

Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data (AI, Data and Robotics Partnership)
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PANDORA

A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of
Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation

D2.2 Architecture and Technical Specifications

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
AIoT	Artificial intelligence of things
WP	Work Package
DOA	Description of the Action
MS	Milestone
ADOA	Adaptive Distribution and Optimization of AI Inferencing in the Cloud-edge Computing Continuum
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	AI as a Service
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robot
APM	Adaptive Project Management
CaaS	Computing as a Service
CAD	Computer-aided Design
CIM	Continual Inference Networks to Speed Up the Inference of DL Models
CRV	Self-validated, Causal, Robust, and Resilient Continuous Learning for Long-term Autonomy and Intelligence
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
D#.#	Deliverable #.#
DACL	Semi-automated Annotations, Labelling and Self-supervised Completion and Augmentation
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DEL	Leveraging Domain Knowledge for Explainable Learning
DICE	Domain-informed, Causal and Explainable AI Based on a Hybrid Learning Reasoning Approach for Continuous Learning
DL	Deep Learning
DOA	Description of the Action
DRFEC	Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component
EP	Early Prototype
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
FL	Federated Learning
FRL	Federated Representational Learning
FRLM	Federated Representational Learning of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations
GENEOs	Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators

GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IM	Intent Manager
IoT	Internet of Things
LID	Local Intrinsic Dimensionality
M#	Month #
ML	Machine Learning
MS	Milestone
NeRF	Neural Radiance Fields
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
P-D-FL	Parallel, Distributed and Federated Learning
PINN	Physics Informed Neural Networks
QU-MAD	Uncertainty Quantification Modelling and Development
R&D	Research and Development
RSRQ	Reference Signal Received Quality
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RSSP	Reference Signal Strength Power
RTSP	Real Time Streaming Protocol
SDG	Synthetic Data Generation
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SPED	Spaces, People, Events, Devices
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
tSDG	Synthetic Data Generation for Time-series Data
UA	User Authentication
UC	Use Case
V&V	Verification & Validation
vPLC	Virtual Programmable Logic Controller
vSDG	Synthetic Data Generation for Vision Data
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

PANDORA aims to develop a comprehensive AI-based and domain-informed framework, with the objectives of (1) improving the preparation and the delivery of complete and trustworthy datasets for training and enhancing AI models deployed in AIoT systems, and (2) increasing the degree of autonomy, trustworthiness, and efficiency for deploying and operating these AIoT systems. We address the first objective in Phase 1 of PANDORA with the following strategies: synthetic data generation, semi-annotations of datasets, uncertainty quantification, data summarization, and verification and validation. The second objective is addressed in Phase 2 which comprises AI as a Service (AIaaS) and Computing as a Service (CaaS) components to support continual, energy-efficient, and robust AIoT operation.

The report analyzes each of the components involved in the project, detailing their functionalities, technical specifications, and dependencies. We rely on the 4+1 Architectural View Model to present the PANDORA architecture from different perspectives, including logical, development, process, data, and physical views. The report includes an integration plan that outlines the software engineering approach, including agile and waterfall methodologies, for developing and deploying the PANDORA framework. Finally, we conclude with the technical requirements for each PANDORA component.

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 2 presents an introduction and some basic information about the purpose of the document, and its relations with other PANDORA WPs.

Section 3 presents an overview of the PANDORA framework and analyzes each component in detail. The 4+1 Architectural View Model used to design the PANDORA architecture is also introduced.

Section 4 presents the architectural views and diagrams. These include a high-level logical view of the PANDORA framework, a development view showing component diagram, a process view showing interactions between PANDORA components, a data view for data interactions between components, and a physical view describing how components are deployed across the computing continuum.

Section 5 presents the use case view, showing how PANDORA components are leveraged in specific use cases using use case diagrams and sequence diagrams.

Section 6 presents the software engineering approach for the PANDORA project, highlighting the principles of user-centric design, iterative development, and continuous integration and deployment. Moreover, this section analyzes the technical requirements of each PANDORA component.

Section 7 presents the conclusion of this deliverable.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to delineate the software architecture for the PANDORA framework and provide the detailed plan on how and when the individual technical components will be developed to form a common integrated framework that offers the expected services to its end-users. This deliverable serves multiple key objectives:

- **Framework Establishment:** The document analyses the methodology and the approach that was adopted for establishing a comprehensive and coherent architectural framework that guides the development and integration of various components. The architecture framework segments the system into architectural views and layers to address the viewpoints of different stakeholders.
- **Technical Specifications:** Detailed technical specifications and design principles that will be adhered to throughout the development process are incorporated throughout this document. This includes defining the framework's structure, the relationships between different components, and the technologies and methodologies employed.
- **Methodologies for Scalability and Adaptability:** This document outlines methodologies to handle future growth and associated challenges, ensuring AIoT systems can adapt to changing demands and maintain high performance and reliability. The architecture definition report defines standard ways to interact with various components and also highlights the role of services to facilitate the data exchange between different AIoT systems.
- **Stakeholder Communication:** To provide a clear and detailed architectural blueprint that facilitates communication and understanding among all stakeholders, including the development team, project managers, and external partners. This shared understanding is crucial for coordinated efforts and informed future optimizations.

This document is based on the DoA of the PANDORA, and the project requirements that are thoroughly analysed in D2.3. PANDORA expected capabilities are showcased through various architectural diagrams. Looking ahead, D2.2 establishes a solid foundation for subsequent phases of the project. It paves the way for seamless integration with the other technical work packages, setting the stage for continuous development and implementation of advanced AIoT-based solutions.

2.2 Intended readership

This document is intended to be a source of complete architecture and technical specifications of PANDORA. It provides a conceptual view of the PANDORA architecture, its core components and their interactions, and sequence diagrams that demonstrate the applicability of PANDORA in realistic use cases. Different views based on design-time and runtime operations are provided. Members of the Project Team may leverage this document to drive the implantation of their components, the interactions between components, as well as the overall PANDORA framework.

2.3 Relationship with PANDORA WPs & managerial organization

This report details the work conducted under Work Package 2. It is related to the integration and deployment of technologies developed in Work Packages 3 and 4 into a unified technological solution. D2.2 focuses on providing the common design guidelines and the framework for the realization of the integrated PANDORA solution. The respective deliverable falls under the MS1 milestone of the project and acts as a mechanism to verify that research & development is progressing according to the initial plan. IMT leads the respective task & deliverable, however, all

partners have contributed to the architecture definition of the PANDORA system and the design of the various architectural views. R&D partners contributed with their expertise to analyze the core interactions and data flows within the PANDORA framework while the industrial partners ensured that the framework architecture was designed to address real industrial requirements.

The current deliverable is intended to set the foundation for the upcoming technical deliverables, more specifically:

- D3.1 – PANDORA scientific foundations for trustworthy training datasets I: shows how AI-based techniques can be applied to a real dataset (of a smart space ecosystem) to deliver a trustworthy and customizable dataset.
- D3.2 – PANDORA scientific foundations for trustworthy training datasets II: an updated and extended version of D3.1.
- D4.1 – Innovative methods, techniques, and services for AIoT systems I: presents the methods, techniques and services that ensure the continual autonomous, robust, and energy-efficient operation of AIoT systems.
- D4.2 - Innovative methods, techniques, and services for AIoT systems II: an updated and extended version of D4.1.
- D5.2 – PANDORA integrated framework shows the initial integrated framework for the PANDORA project.
- D5.3 – PANDORA complete and trustworthy data pipelines. This deliverable shows the integrated framework, data pipelines, technical evaluation and sharing customizations.
- D6.1 – Instantiation of PANDORA pipelines in industrial settings. This deliverable shows the validation scenario alignment, architectural blueprints for trial cases, and self-validation.

2.4 Structure of the document

This deliverable is organised in the following manner to ensure clarity and coherence:

- Section 3: PANDORA Framework Overview. This section showcases the main functionalities and services that the framework is expected to deliver to its end-users. It also entails the individual technical specifications of the main components that constitute the PANDORA framework. The section concludes with the methodology used to assemble various architectural elements in order to satisfy the major functionality and performance requirements of AIoT systems.
- Section 4: Architectural Views & Diagrams. In order to eventually address the challenging architecture of the PANDORA framework this section consists of 5 main views, each of which reflects a different viewpoint of the framework. Each view is associated with a diagram and highlights specific aspects of the framework that are intended to be conveyed through that perspective.
- Section 5: Indicative Scenarios of Use. This section aims to showcase the runtime and design-time behaviour of the framework during the realisation of the industrial scenarios that are validated in the context of D2.3 [1]. Moreover, it provides a visual representation of how users interact with the framework and serves as a blueprint for understanding the functional requirements of AIoT systems from a user's perspective.
- Section 6: Integration Plan provides the initial integration guidelines of how the individual technical elements will be adapted and integrated in a common framework.
- Finally, section 7 concludes the document and summarises the next plans.

2.5 Inputs to the architecture definition process

Initially, the required inputs for deriving the architecture are the scope, the context and the stakeholder requirements. The mapping of the industrial user requirements to the research and development partners drives the development of technologies to address each requirement under their respective development tasks. Furthermore, the technology partners have already outlined the various challenges and their technical approach to effectively address the user requirements per use case. Thus, there is a concrete and detailed methodology acting as the baseline for the definition of the PANDORA framework architecture. The process of the architecture definition is depicted in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Architecture Definition Process

The first step in the definition process is the identification of use case scenarios. Then, the second step is the collection of the consolidated requirements to form the context in which the framework operates, and the definition of the expected performance from the end-user’s perspective. Note that these steps are defined in D2.3. The next step is to define the technical requirements for each component of the framework with emphasis on the data dependencies for better collaboration among the stakeholders by understanding how each component fits into a larger system. The final step includes the definition of input requirements for each component based on the use case scenarios defined in step 1. The next phase initiates with the identification of the most suitable architectural style - considering the complexity of the PANDORA framework, using established architectural styles ensures that the design is consistent, coherent, and aligned with best practices. Structuring a conceptual architecture facilitates the further decomposition of the system by providing a high-level blueprint that outlines the major components and their relationships. This conceptual framework serves as a guide for breaking down the framework into smaller, more manageable parts, each with a clear role and responsibility. The collaborative evaluation of each view is the last step before concluding with a concrete architectural element.

The architecture is evaluated based on stakeholders' requirements and the extent to which it fulfils these requirements. The evaluation is conducted through an iterative process, incorporating both weekly calls and physical meetings to ensure comprehensive assessment and continuous improvement.

3. PANDORA System Overview

3.1 Overview of PANDORA capabilities

The PANDORA framework enables intelligent use of possibly limited real IoT data and improves AIoT system operation by managing the runtime deployment of AIoT application scenarios. Given a base dataset collected from IoT devices, PANDORA's main goal is two-tiered: (i) generate customizable and trustworthy datasets for model training and testing for AIoT application deployment (Phase 1); and (ii) support AIoT deployment as well as continual, energy-efficient and robust AIoT operation via a series of *AI as a Service (AlaaS)* and *Computing as a Service (CaaS)* components (Phase 2). This is achieved using a **set of strategies (5)** that process collected IoT data of AIoT systems in Phase 1 (prior to AIoT system deployment), as well as a **set of strategies (5)** for training, inferencing and explainability of AIoT systems in Phase 2 (post AIoT system deployment). Note that for the remainder of this document, such strategies will be called "**components**" as part of the PANDORA architecture, along with other components required to complete the architecture in Phase 2.

PANDORA Phase 1 proposes components related to synthetic data generation, semi-annotations of dataset, uncertainty quantification and data summarization. All the components work complementary with one another to produce trustworthy datasets for training, testing and deployment of AIoT systems. Then, in Phase 2, PANDORA offers several AlaaS/CaaS-based components that enable continual, energy-efficient and robust operation of AIoT systems, with an increased degree of autonomy. As part of AlaaS, PANDORA proposes the following subcomponents: (1) AI model registry; (2) AI model selection; (3) AI lifecycle management; (4) AI inferencing; and (5) AI model training. The AI model selection subcomponent includes already trained models from the AI model registry to be used in AIoT systems for AI inference.

PANDORA also introduces an Intent Manager (IM) component for selecting trained models that match the intents requirements provided by AIoT application end-users. Such *intents* may relate to e.g., power consumption of the infrastructure, inference response times, etc. The AI lifecycle management subcomponent monitors the AI model to check for errors in terms of accuracy levels, energy violations, etc. This subcomponent may act as follows: (i) it selects another AI model; (ii) it triggers the AI model training component; or (iii) it may provide feedback for the customisation of the dataset provided in Phase 1 and thus, re-train the same model. While AIoT systems operate in real-time, both AI model training and AI inference subcomponents offer communication with components for privacy preserving and robust AIoT systems, based on provided intents. Table 1 provides a list of PANDORA components (along with references to strategies described in PANDORA WP tasks) while Section 3.2 provides a detailed description of each component, along with interactions with other PANDORA components.

To ensure energy-efficient deployment and operation of AIoT systems, PANDORA proposes the development of components related to CaaS. Smart space ecosystems employ resources in the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum where AIoT systems or services can be deployed based on the provided intent requirements. AIoT or AI service requirements will be defined in the form of "find me compute nodes of type GPU for AI inference within X sec, Y power consumption of the infrastructure". Such requirements will be received by the CaaS Performance Estimator

subcomponent to estimate metrics such as power consumption, response times, etc., in a chosen compute node or set of resources (nodes). After the performance estimation, the Resource Provider subcomponent of CaaS chooses the appropriate computing resources. The models are assumed to be benchmarked beforehand to determine appropriate placement on IoT, Edge or Cloud nodes. Each of the components is designed considering the computing continuum infrastructure, and it will be implemented at an appropriate infrastructure level of the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, considering the energy, storage, and movement costs, in both Phases 1 and 2.

Table 1. Overview of the Components

Component Name	Abbreviation	Task / Strategy
Synthetic data generation for time-series data	tSDG	Strategy 1; Task 3.1
Synthetic data generation for vision data	vSDG	Strategy 1; Task 3.1
Uncertainty quantification modelling and development	QU-MAD	Strategy 2; Task 3.2
Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning	DEL	Strategy 3; Task 3.3
Semi-automated annotations, labelling and self-supervised completion and augmentation	DAFL	Strategy 4; Task 3.4
Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component	DRFEC	Strategy 5; Task 3.5
Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence	CRV	Strategy 7; Task 4.1
Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning	DICE	Strategy 9; Task 4.2
Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations	FRLM	Strategy 8; Task 4.3
Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models	CIM	Strategy 10; Task 4.4
Adaptive distribution and optimization of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum	ADOA	Strategy 11; Task 4.5
User Authentication	UA	Task 5.4
AI as a Service	AlaaS	Task 5.4
Computing as a Service	CaaS	Task 5.4
Intent Manager	IM	Task 5.4

3.2 Components analysis

Section 3.1 provides a high-level description of the system architecture, highlighting the main components and their roles. Following this, each subsection will focus on an individual component, providing a high-level technical analysis and detailing the specific services it provides at Phase 1 and Phase 2. Updates regarding the cross-component dependencies and the required

inputs are included in each subsection. This structured approach ensures clarity and coherence, facilitating a better understanding of complex interactions within the system.

The objective of Section 3 is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how each component functions, interacts with other parts of the framework, and contributes to the overall performance and capabilities of AIoT systems. By the end of this section, readers will have a thorough understanding of the technical intricacies of PANDORA and the valuable services rendered by each component. This knowledge is crucial for appreciating the framework's overall functionality and for identifying potential areas for improvement or optimization.

In PANDORA, a Verification & Validation (V&V) subcomponent will be implemented for each PANDORA component based on their inputs/outputs. For more details about how V&V is implemented, please refer to Deliverable D2.3.

Synthetic data generation (SDG)

tSDG Component

Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT) systems and their respective services/applications require a large amount of real data at scale to increase their accuracy, robustness, and sustainability. However, real-world data is often difficult to acquire due to privacy concerns, high costs, or scarcity in certain environments. The **time-series Synthetic Data Generation (tSDG)** component is designed to address the challenge of limited availability of real-world data. When the available real data is insufficient, tSDG can generate customizable synthetic datasets via an event-driven approach. tSDG exploits an ML-based learner component to define the SPED (Spaces, People, Events, Devices) semantic models [5] of the corresponding space. The semantic models, in turn, can be used to generate various synthetic datasets that capture occupancy of spaces, trajectories of occupants and consequent device (sensor) observations such as occupancy, movement patterns, and sensor readings, based on event-driven approaches.

tSDG uses two types of data: (1) regular data describing normal operation of smart space entities; (2) anomalous data describing unseen situations of smart space entities under extreme events. The component receives as input an IoT dataset derived from the smart space ecosystem, along with domain knowledge such as floor plans, and produces a realistic synthetic dataset as output. Both input and output datasets are processed in a time series format, capturing the evolution of information across the three layers of the smart space ecosystem: the application, network, and device layers.

To create these datasets, change point detection algorithms identify discrete events and people, while methods like agglomerative clustering are employed to build the corresponding SPED models that simulate sensor data such as occupancy, temperature, and more. Additionally, synthetic data related to performance metrics is generated using programmable network semantic models. This approach allows AIoT systems to obtain realistic synthetic data in situations where gathering real-world data is challenging, ensuring the continued development and testing of AI models in diverse environments.

tSDG Challenges:

- Generate realistic synthetic data for PANDORA use cases providing time series datasets.
- Acquiring representations of domain knowledge for the considered PANDORA use cases.
- Understanding regular vs. anomalous operation of smart space ecosystems.
- Assess the realism/quality of anomalous events produced from tSDG.
- How to model hypothetical changes in smart space ecosystems and assess its realism.

Table 2. Detailed Description of SDG and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T3.1
Task Leader	IMT
Component Name	time-series Synthetic data generation (tSDG)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	Generates realistic and customizable datasets for AIoT model training through event-driven simulations of time-series data.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Design Time (phase 1)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	Possible input from DACL & DRFEC components
Format of Expected Input	Time series IoT datasets and domain expert knowledge in CSV format.
Triggered by	N/A
Interfaces	No
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	A realistic synthetic dataset consisting of time-series data across device, network, and app layers in CSV format.
Output Data to Partner	Possible output to DEL & QU-MAD components
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Yes
Nature of Expected Output	A customizable, realistic synthetic dataset in time-series format for use in AIoT model training.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as PyTorch, pandas, numpy, scikit.
Hardware Requirements	CPU Intel i7 (or similar), GPU (if Deep Learning will be used), 32GB RAM, Storage >= 512 GB
Communications	RESTFul APIs
Special Communication Requirement	None
Integration Requirements	N/A
Deployment Requirements	Dockerized or started as standalone python software

As depicted in Figure 2, the tSDG component is architected using different layers. At the input and modeling layer, a domain expert extracts attributes from the IoT dataset across application, network and device layers (e.g., bandwidth and failure types). In addition, this layer also provides domain knowledge related to events occurring under normal or extreme conditions. Finally, information related to time and user perspectives will be defined for generating the output data. The learning layer provides *Learners* to extract distributions of attributes at the three layers, or relationships between the attributes. The scenario building layer receives as input the domain experts' information (domain knowledge and configuration parameters) to perform distribution sampling under normal or extreme situations. Finally, input information and extracted patterns are given as input to state-of-the-art data generators. The output of tSDG is an IoT dataset that can be used to train AI models.

Figure 2. High-level Diagram of tSDG

vSDG Component

The vSDG component is used to generate synthetic data from limited visual input data simulating real-world conditions and introducing defects to improve the performance of automated visual quality inspection. By using synthetic data, it's possible to significantly reduce the lead time needed to gather training data allowing the automated inspection system to be quickly adapted to new products without the need for large amounts of new real-world data.

The main functional blocks comprise using as input a sample of real-world images around the object to be inspected and the 3D models of the objects further exploiting NeRF (Neural Radiance Fields) and Gaussian splats [6] to generate new views and images of the object under various conditions. In addition, synthetic defects may be added to simulate potential anomalies and diverse defects. Augmentation techniques can be further included in the rendered set to expand the datasets with realistic visual effects. The dataset is used to train a classification algorithm capable of inspecting and identifying defective products in real-world scenarios.

The approach for implementing this component contains specification of anomalies and sample visual data from the use case provider, along with 3D object models for the objects of interest. The computing platform will have GPU support, and a methodology will be developed to automate training data generation using NeRFs and Gaussian splats for newly introduced objects. The innovation lies in creating a framework that allows for automatic training data generation tailored to different objects and categories of defects. This framework will provide the flexibility to generalize to newly introduced ones.

vSDG Challenges:

- Generate realistic synthetic images for different types of products.
- Assess the quality novel view rendering and the simulation of potential defects.

Table 3. Detailed Description of vSDG and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T3.1
Task Leader	NTUA
Component Name	virtual Synthetic Data Generation(vSDG)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	It generates synthetic data from limited visual input to simulate real-world conditions and introduce defects, reducing the need for extensive real-world data collection for automated visual quality inspection
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Design Time (phase 1)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	Possible input from DACL component
Format of Expected Input	Image data, calibration data, camera poses and object 3D model.
Triggered by	N/A
Interfaces	No
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Synthetic images and training data sets.
Output Data to Partner	Possible output to QU-MAD, CRV, CIM
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Yes
Nature of Expected Output	Synthetic visual data used to train classification algorithms.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Linux environment, PyTorch, C++, CUDA, ONNX Runtime
Hardware Requirements	CPU cores (physical) ≥ 14, RAM ≥ 32GB, storage ≥ 1TB, NVIDIA, GPU (VRAM ≥ 24GB, Compute Capability ≥ 8.6)
Communications	N/A
Special Communication Requirement	None

Integration Requirements	N/A
Deployment Requirements	Docker, network connectivity, remote access control

As shown in Figure 3, the vSDG component exploits images and 3D models to generate synthetic data from a limited number of images. By exploiting on one end the geometric prior of the object to render different viewpoints and on the other hand appearance information from few images it aims to bridge the synthetic to real gap. In addition, methods on realistic novel view synthesis are exploited to generate realistic views from limited number of images. Outputs from both submodules are ingested to the component that learns defect-free distribution for pose agnostic anomaly detection.

Figure 3. High level diagram of vSDG

Uncertainty quantification modelling and development (QU-MAD)

Within the various smart environments where AIoT systems are deployed, there is a need for transparent and trustworthy AI decisions. The Uncertainty Quantification Modelling and Development (QU-MAD) addresses this need by providing a technique for uncertainty quantification using either real or synthetic data. The task will be first implemented via the development of methods such as Bayesian Networks or Scenario Analysis, that elicit the inherited and propagated uncertainties present in the data and the AI models. Then the uncertainties present in data and models will be quantified by using Bayesian and Ensemble approaches. Additionally, the development of visualizations will help communicate these uncertainties clearly to end-users. A user-feedback mechanism will be introduced to annotate user-trust on the uncertain data and models following human-in-the-loop concepts. Note that such human-in-the-loop concepts may concurrently adapt and improve the underlying AI models at runtime, as per the needs of the end-users.

QU-MAD Challenges:

- Identifying and quantifying uncertainties in AI models and data.
- Communicating uncertainties effectively to end-users.
- Finding domain experts for integrating user feedback to annotate and adapt models.

Table 4. Detailed Description of QU-MAD and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T3.2
Task Leader	DLR
Component Name	Uncertainty quantification modelling and development (QU-MAD)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	This component aims to extract, quantify, and communicate the uncertainties from data and AI models in AIoT systems using Bayesian and Ensemble approaches. Additionally, it incorporates a user-feedback mechanism to annotate and adapt based on user trust, ultimately improving AI model performance and trustworthiness.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Design Time (phase 1)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	Input data from SDG
Format of Expected Input	Raw data from AIoT system; synthetic generated data
Triggered by	N/A
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback.
Output Data to Partner	Phase 2
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Yes
Nature of Expected Output	Uncertainty quantification, graphical visualizations, and retrained AI models.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python 3.9 or more, ML frameworks and libraries (PyTorch, Lightning GDAL, Gradio, ...)

Hardware Requirements	GPU with CUDA is recommended
Communications	N/A
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	N/A
Deployment Requirements	Python source code in a GitHub repository

As shown in Figure 4, the component takes as input two data sources: (i) data from IoT devices and (ii) data generated from the SDG component. The combined dataset is used to train machine learning models. During this stage, several methodologies can be used, such as Bayesian Network Approaches and Ensembling Methods. With the trained model, we can disentangle the uncertainty into three categories: Aleatoric Uncertainty, which refers to the inherent randomness in the data, Epistemic Uncertainty, referring to the lack of information about the model or data, and Credal Uncertainty, that captures both previous uncertainties but provides a wider range of outcomes.

Then a graphical user interface (GUI) is used to visualize the uncertainties. Users can visualize visual representations (in case of image data), plots and Metrics. By analyzing the uncertainties, we can identify which samples require more examples in the training dataset. This is where the human-in-the-loop process becomes crucial. Newly identified data points that need more examples will be collected and annotated. This annotation can be performed by human experts and/or through the semi-automated data labeling from PANDORA. Once the new, annotated samples are integrated into the initial training dataset, we can retrain the model, measure the uncertainties, visualize them and add more annotated data if needed. This iterative process enhances the model's accuracy and overall performance.

Figure 4. High-level Diagram of QU-MAD

Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning (DEL)

In AIoT systems, the need for explainability is necessary to ensure trust, transparency, and informed decision-making. The DEL PANDORA component focuses on leveraging domain knowledge to enhance the quality and wealth of the training data. This component primarily operates in an offline mode (PANDORA Phase 1) and utilizes domain knowledge, represented through ontologies, knowledge bases, rules, and physical laws, to improve both the accuracy of AI inference and the discovery of meaningful explanations. The component is divided into two subcomponents as described in what follows.

In the first subcomponent (Enhancing Learning Explainability by Leveraging Geometrical Symmetries Through GENEOS), Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators will be used to reduce the dimensionality of the data, using the symmetries associated with the problem considered. To this end, small libraries of operators sensitive to the presence of appropriate data patterns will be created and convex combinations of these operators will be used to build more complex GENEOS, suitable for analyzing the available information in an explainable way, exploiting the intrinsic interpretability of the GENEOS used. A precise mathematical concept of explainability associated with the approximation of operators through small GENEOS networks will also be developed and applied.

The second subcomponent (Incorporating Domain Knowledge into Causal Explanations for Observational Data) aims to incorporate domain knowledge into the explanation derivation process, including rules and constraints that can refine and support causal analysis. Furthermore, we will seek to derive from the multivariate time series all the minimal-size subsets whose past leads to an optimal predictive model for the future (forecasting) of a given target variable. Identifying all solutions to the variable selection problem leads to gaining insights, domain intuition, and a better understanding of the data-generating mechanism; it is often the first step in causal modeling. The advantages of the proposed models will be demonstrated through comparative evaluations against non-domain-informed models.

DEL Challenges:

- Identification of suitable GENEOS libraries for the problems at hand.
- Mathematical formalization of the concept of "operator A explained by an operator B" through GENEOS theory.
- Implementation of a method to explain an operator A by an approximation B given by a suitable convex combination of GENEOS.
- High complexity for enumerating all causes.
- Lack of ground truth for evaluation.
- Integration of domain knowledge into the explanation process.

Table 5. Detailed Description of DEL and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T3.3
Task Leader	UNIBO
Component Name	Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning (DEL)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	Develops domain-specific explainable AI models by leveraging geometrical symmetries and incorporating domain knowledge to enhance interpretability and causal explanations.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Both
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes

Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	SDG, DACL
Format of Expected Input	Time/Data series, domain knowledge (rules, knowledge graphs), learning tasks.
Triggered by	N/A
Interfaces	No
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Libraries of GENEOS and/or causal structures
Output Data to Partner	DICE, CRV
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Yes
	Insights into the data generation process, the spatiotemporal invariants of the data, its typical patterns, the relationships among the time series variables, and the causal structure of the data with respect to the task's target variable.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	ML libraries
Hardware Requirements	CPU with 4 cores and 8 threads (or similar), NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU (or similar), 64GB RAM, Storage >= 512 GB SSD.
Communications	None
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	N/A
Deployment Requirements	N/A

As depicted in Figure 5, the DEL component accepts in the input a clean time series, along with domain knowledge, in the form of knowledge graphs or rules. It also requires as input a target variable from the time series, so as to investigate a specific task. The user can also specify whether they need explanations to be produced by the first or the second subcomponent. Internally, depending on the existing domain knowledge in the input, the DEL component will compute two kinds of insights into the data generation process; the first subcomponent returns the family of GENEOS specialized for the target variable and the second subcomponent returns all the causal feature subspaces that are linked with a cause effect relationship with the target variable. The output of the component can be fed as input to the DICE component (described later in this section) to guide the local explanation process for specific predictions in Phase 2, and to the CVR component (described later in this section) to aid with the optimization of the model training.

Figure 5. High-level Diagram of DEL

Semi-automated annotations, labelling and self-supervised completion and augmentation (DACL)

This component aims to provide novel approaches for data augmentation, completion and labeling that incur reduced pre-processing and human effort. Semi-automated annotation and labelling techniques will be used to achieve this. To account for heterogeneity and bias in the available data, domain adaptation and transfer learning techniques will be employed. Finally, to ensure the quality of the labelled data, quality control mechanisms such as outlier detection and anomaly detection will be utilized. DACL will be built in Python programming language using its object-oriented features (classes, inheritance, etc.). Existing Python machine learning libraries and frameworks (scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, NetworkX) will be used as basic machine learning building blocks.

The DACL component introduces several key innovations, including missing value inference through transfer learning and missing label inference using graph learning algorithms and models, such as graph-native clustering, classification algorithms, and graph neural networks. It also incorporates quality control through anomaly detection using unsupervised hybrid models that combine different machine learning approaches, including representational learning and clustering. Additionally, DACL enhances data augmentation with novel oversampling techniques that consider local intrinsic dimensionality and the hubness properties of data points.

DACL Challenges:

- missing data in tabular and timeseries datasets.
- missing labels in tabular and timeseries datasets.
- insufficient number of data instances, unbalanced training datasets.
- anomalous data instances.

Table 6. Detailed Description of DACL and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T3.4
Task Leader	UNSPMF
Component Name	Semi-automated annotations, labelling and self-supervised completion and augmentation (DACL)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	Addresses challenges in tabular and time-series datasets by inferring missing data and labels, detecting anomalies, and

	augmenting data.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Design Time (phase 1)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M33
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	No
Input Data from other Components	No
Format of Expected Input	Training dataset in CSV format
Triggered by	N/A
Interfaces	No
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	An enhanced training dataset that has missing data and labels filled in, anomalies detected, and data augmented.
Output Data to Partner	Phase 2
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Yes
Nature of Expected Output	An enhanced training dataset in csv format
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, and NetworkX.
Hardware Requirements	CPU Intel i7 (or similar), 32GB RAM, GPU with CUDA support preferable
Communications	No
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	N/A
Deployment Requirements	Can be either dockerized or started as standalone python software

As shown in Figure 6, the DACL component consists of 5 subcomponents. Data preprocessing component analyzes input training datasets and transforms them into a suitable form for other DACL subcomponents. For example, it may transform a discrete attribute/feature into several numeric features by the one-hot encoding procedure. Missing values are filled by missing value inference subcomponent that utilizes transfer learning when training neural networks. Missing label inference subcomponent uses graph clustering and graph classification on graph neural networks to impute missing labels. Data can be augmented using a data augmentation

subcomponent which is based on LID/hub-aware oversampling. After filling missing values, labels or augmenting data, outlier detection is performed with representational learning and clustering.

Figure 6. High-level Diagram of DACL

Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component (DRFEC)

In large-scale AI systems, handling massive and diverse data sets is essential to achieving accurate, efficient, and scalable performance. By minimizing data redundancy and reducing complexity, this component ensures that only the most important features of the data are preserved. The main goal of this component is to offer advanced functionality for dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction across one or various types of raw data (images, videos, time series, multimodal inputs, etc.). It will process incoming data to generate reduced-dimension datasets, extract relevant features, and provide metrics quantifying the extent of reduction and complexity.

The design and implementation of DRFEC prioritize flexibility and adaptability to handle diverse datasets effectively. Advanced algorithms for dimensionality reduction, clustering, and feature extraction will be carefully selected, tested, and tailored to the specific characteristics of the input data, ensuring optimal performance and the preservation of critical information. The component’s architecture is modular and scalable, enabling efficient data processing while maintaining versatility to adapt to evolving requirements. Additionally, the DRFEC component will be deployed in a containerized format, such as Docker, to streamline installation, support seamless integration, and ensure scalability for high-throughput applications.

The primary innovation of this component lies in its ability to perform data exploration and analyze feature importance, enabling the selection of the most suitable dimensionality reduction and feature extraction methods. This ensures that only the most essential information is retained, significantly reducing data complexity, dimensions, and size by a substantial percentage. This component not only lightens the computational load for subsequent processing stages but also creates datasets that are both customizable and trustworthy. Additionally, the component introduces metrics to quantify the effectiveness of these reductions, providing crucial insights into data simplification and overall performance.

DRFEC Challenges:

- Handling Diverse Data Types: Efficiently processing and integrating different data formats (images, videos, time series, multimodal, etc.).
- Data Quality and Consistency: Handling variations in data quality and ensuring consistent processing across diverse datasets.
- Method Selection: Identifying and selecting the most suitable reduction and extraction methods based on the characteristics of the input data (e.g., image, video, time series).
- Dimensionality Reduction - Feature Extraction: Reducing the complexity of high-dimensional data while preserving critical information. Identifying and extracting relevant features from raw data to enhance subsequent analyses.
- Scalability: Ensuring the component performs efficiently with large volumes of data.
- Integration: Seamlessly integrating with other systems via the REST API for smooth data exchange.
- Performance Metrics: Choose accurate metrics to quantify dimensionality and complexity reductions.

Table 7. Detailed Description of DSDF and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T3.5
Task Leader	ITML
Component Name	Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component (DRFEC)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	Provides dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while retaining the most essential data information.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Design Time (Phase 1)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M33
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	No. But could be used as well for extra data context
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	No. But SDG's output could be used as DRFEC input (if needed)
Format of Expected Input	Based on the UCs that DRFEC will be used, the expected input can be Structured data (.csv, .xlsx, .json), time series data (.csv, .json), or multimodal data in a combined format in JSON
Triggered by	New data arrival in the collection mechanism (T5.1)
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Processed data with reduced dimensions and complexity, along with metrics quantifying the reduction and complexity. The

	metrics are optional. The output will be either .csv or json.
Output Data to Partner	V&V, Phase 2
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Yes
Nature of Expected Output	The output consists of reduced feature vectors or summarized frames (depending on the data type) and numeric metrics (optional) representing dimensionality reduction and complexity. The output will be either .csv or json.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, numpy.
Hardware Requirements	CPU Intel i7 (or similar), GPU (if deep learning will be used), 32GB RAM, Storage >= 512 GB
Communications	Rest APIs
Special Communication Requirement	None
Integration Requirements	N/A
Deployment Requirements	Can be either dockerized or started as standalone python software

As shown in Figure 7, the DRFEC component is comprised of several interconnected modules, each contributing to the overall goal of producing a dimensionally reduced dataset with the most relevant features. This component is closely linked with the data collection mechanism (described in T5.1, subcomponent of AlaaS described later in this section), which collects data from diverse sources. Initially, data flows into a Message Broker, which manages and routes streams from various sources into the pipeline. Once routed, the DRFEC process starts. The first step is handled by the Preprocessing Component, which receives data from the AlaaS subcomponent, formats the incoming data into a standardized structure, and normalizes it to ensure consistency across different types of data. Next, the data is passed to the Cleaning Component, where noise is filtered out, and missing values are addressed to maintain the integrity and quality of the dataset. The Data Fusion Component then combines data from multiple sources into a cohesive, unified dataset. After the fusion, the Feature Analysis Component performs correlation analysis to identify relationships between features and evaluates the importance of each feature in predicting outcomes. Finally, the data enters the Dimensionality Reduction & Feature Extraction Component, where advanced techniques are applied to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset, retaining only the most relevant features. The result is an optimized dataset, ready for use in subsequent tasks such as model training and evaluation

Figure 7. High-level Diagram of DRFEC

Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence (CRV)

This component aims to develop techniques for continuous learning to ensure an increased degree of long-term autonomy, robustness and intelligence of AIoT systems. Open world learning classifiers will be employed to increase robustness against unseen disturbances. In addition, self-validation features will be realized in an unsupervised learning framework by cross-checking results from independently trained models, e.g., through a high-precision-high-recall model combination.

The design and implementation of the CRV component will follow an object-oriented analysis and design approach, utilizing appropriate technologies and tools, predominantly in Python, and leveraging widely used machine learning and data processing libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, and pandas. The component will be designed to support continuous learning, focusing on tasks like novelty detection, incremental class learning, and cross-model validation. Its innovation lies in its ability to perform cross-model validation for continuous learning models, employing high-precision, high-recall model combinations to self-validate performance. This allows the system to continuously refine and improve its models based on incoming data, ensuring robustness and resilience in the learning process.

CRV Challenges:

- Novelty detection in incoming training data.
- Incremental class learning for new emerging classes not already defined in current models and model augmentation.
- Incremental model learning.
- Inference engine for trained models.
- Cross-model validation using high-precision high-recall model combinations.

Table 8. Detailed Description of CRV and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T4.1
Task Leader	UNSPMF
Component Name	Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence (CRV)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	Focuses on continuous learning with novelty detection, incremental model learning, cross-model validation, and inference. It supports self-validation of performance using high-precision, high-recall model combinations.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Both
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
Format of Expected Input	Various formats of continuous input data such as discrete values, timeseries, images, streams/video frames.
Triggered by	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	The access to the inference engine, allowing trained models to be used for predictions.
Output Data to Partner	No
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No
Nature of Expected Output	The expected output is trained models and access to the inference engine, enabling partners to utilize the models for predictions and inference.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, pandas).
Software Requirements	Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.
Hardware Requirements	For inference, inference optimized CUDA capable graphics cards; For training, training optimized CUDA capable graphics

	cards;
Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	AlaaS Model Registry, AlaaS Model Inferencing
Deployment Requirements	Docker

As shown in Figure 8, the CRV component consists of several interconnected services which provide the full stack functionality for self-validated, continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence. There are four active services: novelty detection service which detect novel classes in training data; incremental model learning which adapts model to the newly received data; incremental class learning which is active only when enough novel training data is received so it can represent a new class in which case model is adapted to the new class; cross-model validation which validates the trained models with a high-precision, high-recall model combinations. There is also the data registry which stores newly received training data and also in case there is a novel class detected; it is recorded so it can later be used for incremental class learning.

Figure 8. High-level Diagram of CRV

Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning (DICE)

This component aims to develop AI approaches that enable domain-informed, causal and explainable modelling for AIoT continuous systems and together with components DEL will provide a complete solution for offline and online domain-informed AIoT. The component will focus on different ways to incorporate knowledge in learning approaches in a changing environment and with continuous data generation. First, it consists of a hybrid learning-reasoning approach that leverages both data-driven learning and domain knowledge-based reasoning. This approach aims to enable multiple ways for modelling the AIoT systems that can effectively capture the complex causal relationships among the various components of the system. Moreover, the novel definition of continuous explanations based on meta-features shift analysis, will provide more insights on the reasons that trigger changes on inferences through time. Second, in the context of physics, the field of Physics Informed Neural Networks (PINN) will be investigated to add physical knowledge inside the network architecture to properly deal with physical laws. Environment/context/uncertainty constraints will be used not only to guide the inference, but also

the explanation discovery process. The ultimate goal of this task is to achieve robust and trustworthy AIoT systems that can be effectively operated and maintained in various complex and dynamic environments.

First, we will list the tasks, and data characteristics and modalities of the use cases that are pertinent to the component, to categorize the different real time scenarios that we can consider, focusing on predictive maintenance tasks. As our component comes after the deployment of a model, we will also need to obtain the model or prediction techniques from the use cases or previous components in the pipeline of the project. We will gather domain knowledge when existent, and physics rules when pertinent, and build the causal graph based on the observational data and the dependencies between the variables given by the experts. Our local explanation methods will be post-hoc, meaning that we need to also know the prediction or the data point to be explained. Then, we will build a hybrid statistical explanation framework, which will reveal the most important features and changes in their interconnected distributions that are responsible for the prediction or observation, empowered by the domain knowledge. Finally, we are going to evaluate the explanations on the desired explanation properties (completeness, conciseness, etc.) by the domain experts.

We aim to provide new causal explainability methods built not only on the observations, but also on the environment knowledge for better explanation accuracy. Adapting to the dynamic, continuous environment, our explanations framework will be designed in an incremental manner (when possible, by the setting), for better performance. This context can guide us to design novel, contrastive explanation types, which explains why a prediction was produced instead of another, but also why a prediction was produced in a specific point in time, when another specific prediction was produced in another point in time.

DICE Challenges:

- High complexity of the problem of enumerating causes.
- Lack of ground truth for evaluation.
- Integration of (dynamic) domain knowledge into the explanation process.
- Real time computation.
- Data glitches and data synchronization problems.

Table 9. Detailed Description of DICE and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T4.2
Task Leader	CYU
Component Name	Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning (DICE)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	The component focuses on providing explainability for AIoT systems after the inference phase.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Both
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes

Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	SDG, CRV, FRL, CIM, DEL
Format of Expected Input	Data (e.g., time series, data series); domain knowledge (e.g., rules, knowledge graphs); learning tasks (e.g., predictive maintenance, concept drift detection); learning algorithms; anomaly or prediction to explain.
Triggered by	Anomaly detection
Interfaces	N/A
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Explanations including feature subsets, causal explanations, libraries of Geneos
Output Data to Partner	CRV
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No
Nature of Expected Output	The output includes various forms of explanations designed to make AI decisions more transparent and interpretable
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, pandas).
Software Requirements	Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.
Hardware Requirements	None
Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	AlaaS Model Registry, AlaaS Model Inferencing, AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
Deployment Requirements	Can be either dockerized or started as standalone python software

As shown in Figure 9, the DICE component accepts in the input the trustworthy time series produced in Phase 1, along with domain knowledge, in the form of knowledge graphs. Moreover, when available, the component accepts as input the GENEOS or the causal graphs computed on the dataset by the DEL component. Since the DICE component produces explanations for specific predictions, we need as input also the prediction/detection model from the AlaaS component (described later in this section), that has been trained over the dataset, as well as the test point and the prediction produced for this data point by the model. Optionally, the DICE component accepts user profile parameters, for user-category targeted explanations. The DICE component statistically analyses all the input information, and produces explanations in the form of feature relevance, causal explanations, or GENEOS libraries.

Figure 9. High-level Diagram of DICE

Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations (FRLM)

This component aims to develop Federated Representational Learning (FRL) techniques that can be applied in AIoT systems to enable efficient representation and learning of data. A parallel, distributed and federated (P-D-FL) learning system will be introduced to split among the edge-based compactification sub-models and the server-based FRL system. At the server-based level, the FRL system orchestrates the edge-level blocks and performs training of the global model. Several representational methods will be considered, including autoencoders. The P-D-FL solution enables scaling up and speeding up data analysis processes in the context of scientific simulation or fault detection scenarios and facilitates exchanging data between operators and inspectors.

Following the state-of-the-art analysis of techniques for anomaly detection in federated environments using representational learning, a design for such a system has been set in place. It involves multiple components both in the edge and the cloud including: web servers, clients for training machine learning models, and data and object stores. The component introduces several innovations, including learning lower-dimensional data representations in federated environments and applying unsupervised learning methods for outlier detection based on representational learning. It extends state-of-the-art unsupervised attention-based outlier detection techniques for federated settings and enhances scalability by training classification-based predictive models on compact data representations, addressing issues related to the curse of dimensionality.

FRLM Challenges:

- Learning lower-dimensional data representations from existing datasets.
- Unsupervised training of outlier/anomaly detection models based on such latent lower-dimensional data representations.
- Supervised training of predictive classification-based models on compact data representations.
- Applying previous techniques effectively in federated environments with potential data exchange or privacy-preserving constraints.
- Extending existing methods of outlier detection for federated learning environments.

Table 10. Detailed Description of FRLM and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T4.3
Task Leader	SAG
Component Name	Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations (FRLM)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	This component aims to enable federated (representational) learning (FRL) within the PANDORA ecosystem. It consists of two main parts: the FRL server and the FRL Edge.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Both
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	No
Input Data from other Components	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
Format of Expected Input	Datasets uploaded from edge devices and configuration inputs for the FL training component.
Triggered by	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	A global data representation model that can be exploited for outlier detection in unsupervised learning settings and for classification in supervised learning settings.
Output Data to Partner	No
Output Data to Knowledge Base	AlaaS Model Registry
Nature of Expected Output	The trained models and real-time inference results.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python with libraries and frameworks such as pandas, numpy, scikit-learn, Keras and flwr.
Software Requirements	Python with corresponding libraries and frameworks.
Hardware Requirements	FRL Edge -- Lightweight devices with CPU for edge node training of ML models in federated mode. FRL Server – 32 GB RAM, Multi-core processor (8-16 cores)

Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	AlaaS Model Registry, AlaaS Model Inferencing
Deployment Requirements	Docker

Figure 10 depicts the component setup of the FRLM system. It consists of multiple software systems grouped into server and client-side components. In FL, data collection occurs at the edge, consequently, data storage is also done at the edge. FRL models are optimized by each participating client (edge node) locally, using local data. The training process, which includes numerous edge nodes, is coordinated by the FL coordinator, a server-side component. Model updates are aggregated by the FL coordinator, and the aggregated model first persisted in a model store, following which it is redistributed to the edge nodes. The models in FRL aim to learn a lower dimensional data representation of the original data being collected by individual clients. The aggregated FRL models are validated at the edge, on the validation datasets provided by the clients which participate in model training.

Figure 10. High-level Diagram of FRLM

Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models (CIM)

This component aims to speed up the inference of DL models by developing techniques for efficient inference of AIoT input streams at operation time using the models trained in the design phase. CIM models and visual stream processing will be leveraged to address this issue by enabling the construction of highly optimized inference pipelines that can execute complex models with low latency and high throughput. CIM drive the development of specialized operators to perform inference more efficiently than generic operators. For achieving high performance and improved speed in stream data classification, deep learning models exploiting Continual Inference Self-Attention blocks or Continual 3D (space and time) Convolution blocks will be trained.

CIM Challenges:

- Inference speed: the processing time of continual inference needs to be lower compared to that of the current approach based on rolling (time) window stream classification.

- Memory consumption: improving processing speed often leads to higher memory consumption. Limiting the increase in memory for providing competitive performance is a targeted challenge.
- Classification performance: improving processing speed often compromises the obtained classification performance. Retaining performance while improving processing speed is a targeted challenge.
- Inconsistent input stream: when continual streams are processed, data capturing and transfer can lead to delayed or lost data frames/snippets (e.g., images or sensor recordings). From the processing/classification side, this can be solved by buffering input frames/snippets and processing them with a delay.
- Corrupted inputs. From the processing/classification side, this can be identified at the decoding stage and replaced with empty data frames/snippets or skipped entirely.
- Slow model inference due to resource constraints or hardware allocation. Can be solved by resetting continual inference if the latency becomes too high or by using every n-th input, reducing time-resolution of the model, but keeping the real-time operation of the system.

Table 11. Detailed Description of CIM and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T4.4
Task Leader	AU
Component Name	Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models (CIM)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	The component provides efficient, frame-by-frame classification or regression for sequence data, such as image sequences or time-series streams, enabling low-latency and high-throughput inference for AIoT systems.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Run Time (Phase 2)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M33
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	AlaaS
Format of Expected Input	Image sequence stream (images in PNG/Jpeg/Raw format); time series (sensor recording streams in binary format formed by data frames of duration 1, 0.5, 0.1, etc. seconds, depending on the use case requirements); network video stream (RTSP).
Triggered by	AI Inferencing
Interfaces	No
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Classification or regression results in real-time with each frame

	or snippet of input data.
Output Data to Partner	SAG, PCL, HALCOR
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No
Nature of Expected Output	Classification result (a class label, i.e., an integer number) or a sequence/stream of classification results (one class label per inference output).
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, pandas).
Software Requirements	Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, numpy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.
Hardware Requirements	CPU Intel i7 with 4 cores and 8 threads (or similar), NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU (or similar), 32GB RAM, Storage >= 512 GB SSD.
Communications	In case a network stream is used (for visual or sensor data), the corresponding standard streaming requirements (e.g., RTSP).
Special Communication Requirement	N/A
Integration Requirements	AlaaS: Data Collection Mechanism
Deployment Requirements	Can be either dockerized or started as standalone Python software

Figure 11 provides a schematic representation of the CIM component operation. The Continual Inference model is trained offline using sequence data and corresponding class labels. In the real-time operation, the component is called by the AlaaS component with real-time stream (or time-series) data to provide classification responses. Same data processing is conducted in the training and real-time operation for transforming/normalizing the data to be introduced to the component.

Figure 11. High-level Diagram of CIM

Adaptive distribution and optimization of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum (ADOA)

This component will implement an AI model optimizer that will transform a DL model in a way to fit the application's requirements and the availability and characteristics of the resources to which the DL model can be deployed on. To make the most of the adaptive environment of an IoT-Edge-

Cloud continuum, the component will generate alternative solutions of the DL model architecture, without pretraining it, including the splitting of the model (distributed inference), the pruning of neurons or layers, quantization of the weights, model distillation and early-exit approaches. The component and its configuration will change based on the objectives and their tradeoffs, i.e., considering inference response time minimization, accuracy maximization, optimal use of resources, energy consumption and cost minimization.

The design and implementation of this component will begin by investigating the types of DL models and resource infrastructures the end users plan to utilize. We will also gather user requirements and map them to DL performance indicators. Next, we will collect and assess existing model adaptation techniques applicable to these models. A simulation environment will be set up to test algorithms like model splitting and compression, and technologies such as monitoring agents, resource models, and orchestration software. The best solutions from these tests will be integrated into the final AI model optimizer, which will be validated in various use cases. This component may open the door to real-time adaptation of DL models for resource-constrained devices (like edge devices) without the need to retrain models entirely. Additionally, the component simplifies the complex process of model optimization by providing a developer-friendly interface.

ADOA Challenges:

- Real-time monitoring and feedback loops are necessary to collect data on model performance (in terms of accuracy, speed, and resource usage) and energy efficiency, followed by dynamic adaptation based on that data.
- The optimizer must be able to use a resource model to assess the available hardware capabilities (e.g., CPU, GPU, memory, battery) and adjust the model dynamically.
- Default resource orchestration strategies typically assume an abundance of resources and conduct orchestration operations (scaling, migration, etc) based on resource utilization. In this scenario we need to consider different strategies and integrate them (or replace) with those of a default orchestrator.

Table 12. Detailed Description of ADOA and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T4.5
Task Leader	NTUA
Component Name	Adaptive distribution and optimization of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum (ADOA)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	The component dynamically adjusts deep learning (DL) models to fit specific application requirements and resource constraints, optimizing for factors like inference time, accuracy, resource usage, and energy consumption without retraining the model.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Run Time (phase 2)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M33
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Model architecture (ONNX)

	System/network topology and resource characteristics Prioritized application/data workflow requirements
Input Data from Sensors/Context	No
Input Data from other Components	CaaS, AaaS
Format of Expected Input	ONNX format for DL model description, graph or topology models for infrastructure specification, and a point-based prioritization system for tradeoff approaches.
Triggered by	CaaS
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Optimized DL model solutions including splitting, pruning, quantization, or early-exit approaches.
Output Data to Partner	No
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No
Nature of Expected Output	Optimized DL model configurations suitable for specific hardware and resource constraints.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python libraries, e.g., Pytorch
Hardware Requirements	None
Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	None
Integration Requirements	CaaS subcomponents, AaaS AI model registry
Deployment Requirements	Docker

Figure 12 depicts at a high level the main software component (Model Optimizer) and its inputs and outputs. The key idea is that the Model Optimizer receives the necessary data based on which it must split a DL model and possibly transform its parts. As an output the Optimizer generated actionable deployment plans for the parts of the model: which the parts are, how they can be containerized, in which resources they will be deployed and a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) depicting how the data are orchestrated.

Figure 12. High-level Diagram of ADOA

User Authentication (UA)

This component integrates Keycloak for user authentication through the User Interface. It manages the authentication flow, allowing the user to login and access the system resources. Once authenticated, Keycloak-issued tokens can be included in the requests to the system (or the API Gateway if it is used) to verify the user.

To design and configure the UA component, the exact requirements regarding the user authentication needs to be determined first. In collaboration with other components providing the UI, the login/logout flow, token management, and session handling will be implemented. Requests from the UI (or the API Gateway) will verify the validity of the tokens before proceeding.

UA Challenges:

- Unauthorized access to the system resources

Table 13. Detailed Description of UA and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	Task 5.4
Task Leader	CBRL
Component Name	User Authentication (UA)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	This component integrates Keycloak for user authentication through the UI, manages the authentication flow and provides tokens to verify users for accessing system resources.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Run Time (phase 2).
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	N/A
Input Data from Sensors/Context	N/A
Input Data from other Components	User Credentials from User Interface, Token validation requests from components that need authentication
Format of Expected Input	User Credentials: Structured as key-value pairs (e.g., username/password) sent via secure HTTP requests. Token Validation Requests: JSON-formatted data or HTTP headers containing authentication tokens for validation.
Triggered by	User Interface, components that need authentication
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Authentication Tokens, validation messages
Output Data to Partner	Validation messages
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No

Nature of Expected Output	Tokens for accessing system resources, validation status of tokens, user session status
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	KeyCloak interface, docker engine
Software Requirements	Docker, docker compose, JAVA >=17, Keycloak Docker image
Hardware Requirements	N/A (dependent on deployment environment)
Communications	HTTP/S, RestAPIs, APIs used in PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	None
Integration Requirements	IM for secure access control
Deployment Requirements	Must be deployable as a Docker container, ensuring compatibility with the existing PANDORA infrastructure

Figure 13 shows the flow diagram of the UA. When there is no active session, the user logs in through the User Interface, and Keycloak issues tokens upon successful authentication. Once authenticated, users can send requests to the backend System Component, which verifies the token through UA, before fulfilling the request.

Figure 13. High-level Diagram of UA

AI as a Service (AlaaS)

The AlaaS component serves as the exposure layer for the AI model operations hosted on a central repository. The principal features of the AlaaS are:

- Hosting a set of AI models within AI repository. These models can be AI or rule-based. Hosting the models in a common platform enables the re-use of models across use cases. The models will be developed based on the components within Phase 2.
- Using a model selection function to select a model dependent on the use case requirements. The model selection function can determine the “best” model dependent on accuracy, training/inference time and resource load of the model.

- Training the selected AI model on computing resources provided by the CaaS component (described later in this section). The training will be performed on the IoT, Edge or Cloud resource dependent on performance optimality.
- Inferencing on the trained model with runtime datasets. Inferencing will be done on computing resources provided by CaaS. The inferencing will be performed on the IoT, Edge or Cloud resource dependent on performance optimality.
- In case of deteriorating accuracy or distribution shifts, lifecycle management of the models would be performed within AlaaS. This process may involve re-training or hyper-parameter tuning to match new requirements.

The AlaaS component is envisioned to serve as a data bus layer to coordinate training and inferencing of models within Phase 2 of PANDORA. AlaaS API exposure that can be invoked by multiple use cases and models will have to be implemented. Development of this framework will be done over open-source tools.

AlaaS Challenges

1. Efficient model repository to provide data and model access.
2. Interaction with the requirements module to select the best model.
3. Interaction with the CaaS component for performance evaluation of training/inference.
4. Efficient lifecycle management of components in an autonomous fashion.
5. Standardized API exposure of AlaaS.
6. The data bus implementation allowing interaction between customized training data, runtime data and AI models.

Table 14. Detailed Description of AlaaS and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T5.4
Task Leader	EAB
Component Name	AlaaS
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	software
Short Description	Central AI repository component to host, train and manage AI models with API exposure.
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Phase 2
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes (as customized training data)
Input Data from other Components	Yes (models, CaaS)
Format of Expected Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domain knowledge (symbolic graph) - AIoT goals - Training/runtime data (time series) - Models - CaaS performance counters

Triggered by	Intent Manager
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	AI model inferencing related to AIoT goals generated by the scenario.
Output Data to Partner	Yes (actions, explanations)
Output Data to Knowledge Base	Possible
Nature of Expected Output	Policy or inference outputs.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python AI packages, graph search tools, monitoring tools
Hardware Requirements	Deployment environment
Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	Should receive inputs from data sources, AI models to match intent requirements
Integration Requirements	IM/CaaS subcomponents
Deployment Requirements	Edge/Cloud

The high-level model for AlaaS is presented in Figure 14. The trained models created from Phase 2 components are stored in the model registry. These models may be selected according to the AIoT goals (accuracy, computation) and deployed for inferencing using the CaaS and the IoT-Edge-Cloud resources. The AI model lifecycle management sub-component monitors the output accuracy and model distribution shift to trigger model re-training.

Figure 14. High-level Diagram of AlaaS

Computing as a Service (CaaS)

The CaaS component serves as the computational continuum exposure component. Available computing resources on the IoT Edge (or Fog) and cloud are collated and exposed to the AlaaS

component. The resources may be requested for training, inferencing or lifecycle management of AI models. Efficient performance estimation would be needed to determine the tradeoffs in resource usage, training time, inference time and model accuracy. To develop the component, we will reuse open-source CaaS implementations and tailor make them towards our deployments and scenarios. One or more performance estimation algorithms may be used. It will be crucial to ensure real-time observability of available computing resources over the computing continuum.

CaaS Challenges

1. Observability of computing resources in real-time to ensure optimal deployment.
2. Efficient performance estimation and benchmarking of AI models. Can we prevent under/over estimation of resources?
3. API exposure of functionalities across use cases and model types.

Table 15. Detailed Description of CaaS and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T5.4
Task Leader	EAB
Component Name	CaaS
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software and Hardware (we may emulate compute resources)
Short Description	The CaaS component provides exposure to the compute continuum and ensure resource efficient deployment of model training and inferencing
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Runtime (phase 2)
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	No
Input Data from Sensors/Context	No
Input Data from other Components	AlaaS (model requirements)
Format of Expected Input	Compute resource requirement or equivalent mapping
Triggered by	AlaaS
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	Computing resources for deployment of models.
Output Data to Partner	No
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No
Nature of Expected Output	Resource allocation on edge/fog/cloud.
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python AI packages, graph search tools, monitoring tools

Hardware Requirements	Deployment environment
Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	Should receive inputs from the computing continuum (developed by the platform team)
Integration Requirements	AlaaS/IM subcomponents, ADOA, CIM
Deployment Requirements	Edge/Cloud

Figure 15 showcases the high-level view of the CaaS component. On receiving the model training or inference requirements, the CaaS performs performance estimation and chooses the appropriate computing resources. The models are assumed to be benchmarked beforehand to determine appropriate placement on IoT, Edge, or Cloud nodes. In the case of advanced techniques such as split computing (ADOA component), there may be a ratio of resources proposed across the computing continuum.

Figure 15. High-level Diagram of CaaS

Intent Manager (IM)

The IM component serves as the requirement interface between the AlaaS and the scenario owner. Using an internal knowledge base, it determines the current state of AIoT systems and generates intent issues. These issues are translated to AIoT goals provided to the AlaaS components. This intent manager will be developed using standard python libraries and rule-based issue generators.

IM Challenges

1. Standardized format for intent requirements across use cases.
2. Efficient intent issue generation and goal mapping.

Table 16. Detailed Description of IM and Its Associated Requirements

Related PANDORA task	T5.4
Task Leader	EAB
Component Name	Intent Manager (IM)
Type (Software/Hardware/Both)	Software
Short Description	Receives intent requirements from scenario owner and evaluates intent issues
Utilized at: Design Time (phase 1) / Run Time (phase 2) / Both	Phase 2
Estimated date of first release that can be deployed/integrated	M30
Input requirements	
Input Data from Knowledge Base	Yes
Input Data from Sensors/Context	Yes
Input Data from other Components	Scenario requirements
Format of Expected Input	Requirements in standard format
Triggered by	Scenario owner providing requirements
Interfaces	Yes
Output requirements	
Main Outputs	AIoT goals towards the AlaaS components
Output Data to Partner	No
Output Data to Knowledge Base	No
Nature of Expected Output	Goals in standard format
H/W & S/W requirements	
Development Environment	Python
Software Requirements	Python AI packages, graph search tools
Hardware Requirements	Deployment environment
Communications	APIs and Protocols of PANDORA Integration technologies
Special Communication Requirement	Intent specification to be provided
Integration Requirements	AlaaS subcomponents
Deployment Requirements	Edge

Figure 16 provides a high-level view of the IM component. After receiving the scenario requirements from the scenario owner (via a simple user interface), the knowledge base provides the knowledge graph of the current state of the domain. The issue generator compares the current state to that of the intent and generates issues. These issues are then mapped to specific goals that are communicated to the AlaaS component.

Figure 16. High-level Diagram of IM

3.3 Methodology

Architectural Model

Software architecture deals with abstraction, decomposition and composition, and style and aesthetics. It also deals with the design and implementation of software’s high-level structure. There are several methodologies that aim to capture almost every aspect of a system in one single architectural element and eventually fail to provide a concrete & holistic view of the system. Currently, there is no single architecture that is best for all applications – different architectures have different advantages and disadvantages. It is important to understand those strengths and weaknesses when choosing an architectural approach for a given application. For the selection of the most suitable methodology for the architecture definition of PANDORA, emphasis was given to the following architectural questions:

- How is the framework structured and what are the main functional elements of the PANDORA architecture?
- How will these elements interact with one another and with the environment?
- How does the framework behave during the use case scenarios realisation and what processes take place offline?
- Which are the data requirements of the framework and its components? What information will be managed, stored and presented?
- How will the framework obtain that data from the environment or from the users? What sensors will produce the data? What processes will abstract the sensory data into representations internal to the architecture?
- What hardware and computing infrastructure is required to support the deployment of the PANDORA framework to the use cases?
- What are the critical scenarios selected for the framework architecture?

The current document describes the PANDORA architecture using five concurrent and interrelated views considering the above-mentioned questions and the special needs of AIoT systems. From an architectural standpoint, the most crucial aspect is that AIoT systems must handle large volumes of sensor data asynchronously and in real-time while ensuring robustness, trustworthiness, and energy efficiency in complex, dynamic environments. Moreover, these systems need to be able to adapt across different operational phases – from rapid, real-time data processing to long-term, autonomous decision-making. To handle these requirements, several views were incorporated to include system capabilities depending on the time of operations (design-time & runtime).

The 4+1 View methodology [2] is an ‘architectural style’ to organize an application’s architectural visual representations into views to meet individual stakeholder’s needs and properly address the various concerns. Each view is described by a “blueprint” that represents a system from a different perspective and uses its own particular notation. Figure 17 shows the 6 views utilized for the definition of architecture along with the interests of different stakeholders.

Figure 17. 4+1 Architectural View Model

The 6 views will be further analyzed in terms of their purpose, system functionality and the architectural style. Additional items will be included, such as tables, matrix tables or even supplementary figures to the main diagrams in order to enhance the clarity of each view. Collectively, the views comprehensively describe the entirety of the system.

Modular, Hierarchical Approach

The architecture will be derived based on a hierarchical approach (see Figure 18). The top level is the conceptual architecture diagram, which is what has been presented in the system overview in Figure 17 above. The immediate lower level is the module architecture diagram, where the functional layers are decomposed into software modules while keeping the functionalities defined in the logical view and the conceptual diagram. The next lower level is the mapping of the individual software modules onto the hardware nodes they operate. Since PANDORA will be validated through 5 real-world industrial pilot cases, the lower level aims to showcase the behaviour of the enabled software modules of the PANDORA framework at runtime. Adopting a scenario-driven approach, this document captures the system’s critical functionality - capabilities that are the most important, are used more frequently or present significant technical risk. These capabilities are showcased through the use cases diagrams and reflect the user requirements prioritisation.

Figure 18. Hierarchical Architecture of the Methodology

3.4 Summary

This section provides an overview of the PANDORA framework, as well as a detailed analysis of its components. For each PANDORA component, we provide technical requirements, as well as input/output data requirements. We also provide architectural diagrams for each component highlighting several subcomponents that are part of the overall PANDORA framework. Finally, we conclude this section by providing an overview of the 4+1 Architectural View Model that we follow to create the PANDORA architecture which is presented in Section 4.

4. Architectural Views and Diagrams

This section presents the PANDORA architecture by relying on the 4+1 Architectural View Model. First, a conceptual diagram of the PANDORA framework is presented based on the different phases defined in Section 3. Then, it is demonstrated how the components interact with each other in a component diagram per PANDORA phase, as well as in sequence diagrams using the PANDORA use cases. A more detailed description of the data accepted as input and provided as output from components is also provided. Finally, deployment diagrams are provided to indicate how different components can be deployed in the computing continuum (IoT-Edge-Cloud).

4.1 Logical View – Conceptual Diagram

In general, the logical view focuses on the high-level elements, their interactions & relationships and helps developers, R&D partners and the rest of stakeholders to better understand how the different components of the system interact and work together. It illustrates how the system is decomposed into specific areas of functionality. Finally, the logical view supports the functional requirements — what the system should provide in terms of services to its users.

As already pointed out, the PANDORA framework consists of two phases: (i) Phase 1, which aims at producing customizable and trustworthy datasets for model training and testing for AIoT application deployment, and (ii) Phase 2, which supports AIoT deployment as well as energy-efficient and robust AIoT operation via a series of AI as a Service (AlaaS) and Computing as a Service (CaaS) components. Table 17 shows where each PANDORA component operates.

Table 17. PANDORA Components per phase

Acronym	Phase 1	Phase 2
tSDG	x	
vSDG	x	
QU-MAD	x	
DEL	x	
DACL	x	
DRFEC	x	
CRV		x
DICE		x
FRLM		x
CIM		x
ADOA		x
UA		x
AlaaS		x
CaaS		x
IM		x

PANDORA Phase 1 proposes components related to synthetic data generation, semi-annotations of dataset, uncertainty quantification, data summarization and validation/verification, and explainable modeling. All the components work complementary with one another to produce trustworthy datasets for training, testing and deployment of AIoT systems. Figure 19 depicts the PANDORA high-level architecture for the Phase 1 components. All components (or some of them) can share the same dataset as well as domain-knowledge related to the corresponding smart space ecosystem where AIoT systems are aimed to be deployed. To be more precise, the environment of interest consists of diverse sensorised spaces (office buildings, critical energy infrastructures, factories, etc.). As a first step, PANDORA requires a “seed” real dataset. This could be a small-scale but real dataset captured from devices for a limited period (e.g., data captured from Bluetooth Beacon for a duration of two months in just a single floor of a building). In addition, it requires domain specific knowledge (e.g., scientific benchmarks, existing physics models, physics laws like conservation laws, characterisation of the interaction between particles and the materials that allows the modelling of the physical interaction, etc.). Using the provided IoT dataset and domain specific knowledge, Phase 1 components are leveraged to generate customizable and trustworthy datasets, based on the needs of end-users.

Figure 19. Phase 1 High-level Architecture

In Phase 2, PANDORA offers several AaaS/CaaS-based components that enable energy-efficient and robust operation of AIoT systems, with an increased degree of autonomy. Figure 20 provides the high-level architecture of PANDORA Phase 2. In detail, PANDORA proposes the following components: (1) AI model selection (2) AI lifecycle management, (3) AI inferencing, (4) AI model training, and (5) an AI Model Registry. The AI model selection component includes already trained models to be used in AIoT systems for AI inference. PANDORA aims to introduce an intent-driven approach for selecting trained models that match the requirements provided from domain administrations or AIoT system end-users. Such intents may relate to e.g., power consumption of the infrastructure, inference response times, etc. Intents are handled via the Intent Manager. The AI lifecycle management component monitors the AI model to check for errors in terms of accuracy levels, energy violations, etc. This component may act as follows: (i) it selects another AI model; (ii) it triggers the AI model training component (see below); or (iii) it may provide feedback for the customisation of the dataset provided in Phase 1 and thus, re-train the same model. While AIoT systems operate in real-time, both AI model training and AI inference components offer approaches for privacy preserving and robust AIoT systems, based on provided intents.

To ensure energy-efficient deployment and continual operation of AIoT systems, PANDORA proposes the development of components related to CaaS. Smart space ecosystems employ resources in the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum that AIoT systems or services can be deployed based on the provided intents. The CaaS Performance Estimator subcomponent uses a trained model to estimate metrics related to power consumption, response times, etc. in a chosen compute node or set of nodes. Each of the Phase 2 components is designed considering the computing continuum infrastructure, and it will be implemented at an appropriate infrastructure level of the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, considering the energy, storage, and movement costs, in both Phases 1 and 2.

Figure 20. Phase 2 High-level Architecture¹

4.2 Development View – Component Diagrams

This is a view of a system’s architecture that encompasses the components used to assemble and release the PANDORA framework. The development view decomposes the two phases into individual software components and describes their interactions in order to deliver the functionalities defined in the logical view. The development view adopts a two-fold approach, encompassing both the design-time structure and runtime behavior of the system..

The component diagram’s main purpose is to show the functional and data relationships between the components of the framework. Component diagrams allow an architect to verify that a system’s required functionality is being implemented by components, thus ensuring that the developed system will be acceptable in terms of technical configuration and its initially defined purpose. Within the PANDORA framework, each component is responsible for at least one functionality, which is clearly associated with a basic technical operation, described in Section 4.1. In addition, the development view presented in the form of component diagrams serves the purpose of a useful communication mechanism between the business logic and the technical implementation of the platform, since it provides a visual representation of the high-level components formalizing a roadmap for the development and integration of the PANDORA framework.

¹ Note that the PANDORA User Interface will be leveraged from End-users to define intent requirements only (provided by EAB). Nevertheless, for the HALCOR scenarios only, AEGIS will develop a User Interface for the visualization of data provided from PANDORA.

PANDORA integration technology

To facilitate seamless integration and interaction between PANDORA components, we aim to develop a unified PANDORA integration technology. This technology will be based on the publish/subscribe interaction paradigm using well-known APIs for the IoT, such as MQTT, CoAP and ZeroMQ as well as server implementations such as EMQX, mosquito, etc.

Details regarding the PANDORA integration technology implementation will be provided in D5.1 and D5.2.

Component Diagram for Phase 1

Figure 21 shows the deployment diagram of Phase 1 of PANDORA. Using tSDG or vSDG components, when the seed data is insufficient, PANDORA can generate customizable synthetic datasets via an event-driven approach. Domain knowledge (e.g., semantic models), in turn, can be used to generate various synthetic datasets that capture occupancy of spaces, trajectories of occupants and consequent device (sensor) observations. vSDG supports synthetic images representing cameras. For this, NeRFs will be used to generate additional images from an object or a scene (input dataset). The realistic synthetic data or the real data only, can be accompanied with uncertainty quantification guarantees, i.e., via the QU-MAD component. To enable proper domain knowledge modelling, the DEL component enables AI tools to simultaneously harness the data and domain knowledge and laws in an explainable fashion.

For the real data that exhibits missing information such as, e.g., labels, the DACL component will be employed semi-automatically, and with reduced human effort, make such data complete for consumption by standard AI tools. Finally, the DRFE component takes care of the over-represented system domains where data redundancy is present and carries out summarization and dimensionality reduction over the relevant domains. The outputs of the components mentioned are grouped together, producing an overall complete trustworthy dataset.

Figure 21. Phase 1 Component Diagram

Component Diagram for Phase 2

Figure 22 shows the component diagram of Phase 2. After a trained model is selected, PANDORA proposes the implementation of parallel data pipelines that ensure continual, energy efficient and autonomous AIoT systems at operation time. Every PANDORA component follows a different approach. CRV considers input domain knowledge (from Phase 1) and unseen uncertainties of the smart space ecosystems such as unpredictable faults, errors and adversarial attacks. Another learning data pipeline will be implemented by relying on the FRLM component for handling massive data acquisitions and large-scale simulations. Regarding the support of explainable AI inference as a service, PANDORA provides three novel approaches, grouped under the DICE component. The CIM component uses Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DNN through Continual processing of input streams. A representation of the available IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum will be modelled to provide (near) real-time operation on low-computational power processors. Finally, the ADOA component supports efficient inference of DNN by exploiting the different capabilities in the IoT-Edge/Fog-Cloud continuum. This will be achieved through split computing and/or distributed computing.

Figure 22. Phase 2 Component Diagram

4.3 Process View – Sequence Diagrams

In addition to the four views discussed above, the process view is the central view for capturing scenarios. What was discussed previously mainly refers to the PANDORA framework operation at a more generic level. The Process View aims to delineate the behavior of the framework within specific scenarios. This helps to showcase the flexibility and operation of the framework in the eyes of end-users and other stakeholders. Sequence diagrams provide a valuable option for this aim as they also serve as an initial input for the integration process of PANDORA's components.

We leverage the pilot cases described in D2.3 [1] and their detailed scenarios. These scenarios describe clearly which PANDORA components of both phases are required in order to satisfy User Requirements. This Section groups all scenarios per pilot use case to provide a high-level view on how PANDORA components can be leveraged (see Section 5.1).

In Figure 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, we show the basic workflow for the following scenarios:

- SAG Scenarios: Network and resource management in sorting control
- EAB Scenarios: Communication aware safe robot planning and closed-loop control
- PCL Scenarios: Automated Vision Inspection using product images and models
- FRA Scenarios: Continuous adapted anomaly detection for refueling station
- HALCOR Scenarios: Next-hour(s) consumption prediction

The main focus is the message exchange between different components at a high level of abstraction. Starting from SAG scenarios, they can be summarized from the end-user perspective in the following table.

Table 18. Summary of SAG Scenarios

SAG Scenarios: Network and resource management in sorting control	
Brief Description	In an industrial production cell, networked devices and software components control the correct sorting of work pieces. However, issues such as network congestion or high demand on compute resources (e.g., during shift changes) influence sorting accuracy and overall process efficiency. SAG scenarios focus on forecasting potential delays and resource bottlenecks to conduct proper solutions.
Primary Actors	Technician on Manufacturing Shop Floor.
Pre-conditions	The infrastructure is deployed and properly set-up.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating dataset(s) that enable the creation of AI to predict failures in industrial edge / network infrastructures and computing overloads. • Creating AI model(s) that predict critical failures in industrial edge / network infrastructures • Implement corrective actions, such as reallocation of resources to maintain efficiency.

Figure 23. Sequence Diagram of SAG Scenarios

The sequence diagram of Figure 23 illustrates the process of dynamically optimizing system performance in response to high delay and resource demand using PANDORA. In Phase 1, training data is prepared to include both “normal” and “anomalous” data points that capture potential infrastructure failures. During run-time operation (Phase 2), the data can be retrieved from Phase 1 generated datasets and fed into "Phase 2 components" for continuous learning. The AlaaS component automatically selects appropriate continuous learning and explanation models, which are trained in a federated environment to enhance privacy. Inference results from continuous learning are sent to scenario deployment domain to trigger necessary actuations such as adjustments in resource allocation. Finally, explanations are provided to the actor to enhance trust in the AIoT system’s decision-making.

Table 19. Summary of EAB Scenarios

EAB Scenarios: Communication aware safe robot planning and closed-loop control	
Brief Description	EAB scenarios focus on safe, communication-aware robot planning and closed-loop control to ensure trustworthy 5G connectivity in dynamic environments. The robot uses AI-planning or other applicable techniques to ensure (i) speed, (ii) specific 5G throughput/latency observed, and (iii) collision with obstacles preventions. In addition, it could be possible to change the amount/quality of sensing updates to reduce network load.
Primary Actors	Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) or Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV) administrators.
Pre-conditions	The robot is equipped with a 5G/6G network for real-time communication and data processing.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure the robot is using stable 5G communication and follows the shortest and safest path with appropriate network load to minimize battery consumption, prevent obstacles and adhere to communication constraints.

Figure 24. Sequence Diagram of EAB Scenarios

Figure 24 illustrates the process of safe robot planning with communication quality awareness using PANDORA. Domain knowledge and sensory data about the environment of the robot are collected and used for synthetic data generation and augmentation using tSDG in Phase 1. During the run-time phase, the actor must be authenticated to interact with the framework via UA and IM, where they can specify requirements and receive inference results. IM interprets the user's requirements and communicates with the AlaaS platform for inferencing. AlaaS, in turn, requests computational resources using CaaS to enable continuous learning and generate explanations. The Continuous Learning (CRV) component considers the robot's current status and the user's communication quality requirements to produce a safe planning strategy for the robot as well as configurations to the 5G network controller.

Table 20. Summary of PCL Scenarios

PCL Scenarios: Automated Vision Inspection using product images and models	
Brief Description	To reduce the lead time for new automated visual inspection systems, synthetic image data will be created based on a limited sample of real images, taken with a physical camera setup, from a shaver part & design that need to be inspected. This sample contains good products and a limited set of products with possible visual defects. These pictures are input for synthetic data creation. In addition, synthetic images are rendered and generated from CAD drawings/3D models with and without randomized defects and with environmental influences, i.e. lighting influences, reflections, dust, size and location variations, etc. This synthetic data will then be used to train a classification algorithm to inspect visual quality print designs on shaver parts.
Primary Actors	Conveyer technician.
Pre-conditions	A set of real images, CAD drawings or 3D models (good and defective products) has been captured. Demonstrators set up with cameras and lighting.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create scalable synthetic datasets that accurately represent product quality and potential defect variations. • Reduces lead time for automated vision inspection systems for new products by generating synthesized data.

Figure 25. Sequence Diagram of PCL Scenarios

As shown in Figure 25, in PCL's scenarios, Phase 1 involves generating synthetic data using vSDG based on real images datasets CAD drawings or 3D models provided by the actors. Synthetic data is specifically created to represent potential defects that are not presented in real datasets. Explanations are essential to offer the actor insights into the accuracy of the synthetic images and their annotations. Continues Learning is used in the run-time phase to generate visual inspection AI model for anomaly detection.

Table 21. Summary of FRA Scenarios

FRA Scenarios: Continuous adapted anomaly detection for refueling station	
Brief Description	This scenario focuses on improving operational safety and efficiency at a hydrogen refueling station. It aims to detect early-stage anomalies to prevent risks such as component shutdowns by implementing continuous learning to refine the anomaly detection model over time.
Primary Actors	Hydrogen refueling station components.

Pre-conditions	Sensor-based monitoring systems for temperature, pressure or flow. In addition, some warning data such as error logs would be used.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish explainable anomaly detection for improved safety and reduced shutdowns. Implement continuous learning and integrate feedback from domain experts to reduce false positives and improve detection reliability.

Figure 26. Sequence Diagram of FRA Scenarios

FRA scenarios present a continuous self-adaptive anomaly detection system for the hydrogen refueling station. In Phase 1, synthetic anomalies are generated based on historical error logs and previously predicted anomaly events. This synthetic data along with real-time observations is leveraged to detect potential failures such as shutdowns of the station components. The predictions with its explanations will be further used for future model self-adaptation.

Table 22. Summary of HALCOR Scenarios

HALCOR Scenario: Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	
Brief Description	Prediction of the energy consumption of the extrusion press based on past consumption patterns or planned production schedules.
Primary Actors	System administrators.
Pre-conditions	Access to historical data and energy monitoring systems.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predict energy consumption based on recent and past energy, use of press patterns and/or production plans.

Figure 27. Sequence Diagram of HALCOR Scenarios

Figure 27 shows HALCOR’s scenarios that leverage the PANDORA framework for predicting the next hour energy consumption of the extrusion. Initially, the scenario domain provides real-time observations, past consumption patterns and/or planned production schedules to Phase 1 components for augmented synthetic data generation to enrich and enhance the input data. In Phase 2, it mainly involves energy consumption prediction and result display by web-based GUI (part of the PANDORA IM).

4.4 Data View – Summary Table

The Data View in the PANDORA framework offers a high-level and comprehensive framework that outlines the essential data interactions between the different components. It details the specific inputs required by each component and the corresponding outputs they generate. The Data View, Table 23, facilitates a seamless integration of components by specifying data dependencies while offering a more compact view of the PANDORA framework. The information gathered for this table completes and binds the previous architectural views and is the last step on the hierarchical approach followed. The process of gathering this information per component from all the technology providers was crucial, since the documentation of the interactions strengthens and validates the correlation between the Logical view and the Components view. Additionally, it is an asset to the realization of the initial integration processes.

Table 23. Input and Output of each PANDORA component

Name	ID	Input	Output
tSDG	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time series IoT datasets. - Domain expert knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Device layer with position coordinates and orientation, time series data. - Network layer with SNR, RSSP, RSRQ, RSSI, ping, throughput as a timeseries. - Application layer with domain expert knowledge which can be formulated as constraints.
vSDG	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Few images with and without defects - Camera calibration data - Object 3D models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Synthetic images and training data sets.
QU-MAD	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raw data from AIoT systems (e.g., sensor data, user interactions). - Synthetic generated data used for model learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantified uncertainties in data and models. - Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users. - Adapted AI models based on user feedback.
DEL	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data (Time/Data series). - Domain knowledge (rules, knowledge graphs). - Learning tasks (Predictive maintenance, Concept Drift detection, path planning, etc). - Learning algorithms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of a new mathematical approach to explainability in AI. - Development of libraries of GENEOS for use in XAI. - Explanation (causality graphs, data drifts, feature subspaces, etc)
DACL	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training dataset. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhanced training dataset that has missing

			data and labels filled in, anomalies detected, and data augmented.
DSDF	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structured data (tabular). - Text data. - Images. - Videos. - Time series data. - Multimodal data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Processed data with reduced dimensions – complexity. - Results based on metrics.
CRV	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Various formats of continuous input data (discrete values, timeseries, images, streams/video frames). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trained models and access to the inference engine.
DICE	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data (Time/Data series). - Domain knowledge (rules, knowledge graphs). - Learning tasks (Predictive maintenance, Concept Drift detection, path planning, etc). - Learning algorithms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explanation (causality graphs, data drifts, feature subspaces, etc).
FRLM	9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The datasets uploaded at the edge. - Configuration inputs for the FL training component. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A global data representation model that can be exploited for outlier detection in unsupervised learning settings and for classification in supervised learning settings.
CIM	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Image sequence stream (images in PNG/Jpeg/Raw format). - Time series (sensor recording streams in binary format formed by data frames of duration 1, 0.5, 0.1, etc. seconds, depending on the use case requirements). - Network video stream (RTSP). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The classification result (a class label, i.e., an integer number) or a sequence/stream of classification results (one class label per inference output).
ADOA	11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DL model description in ONNX specification. - Computing/network infrastructure specification in graph, topology models or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimized DL model configurations suitable for specific hardware and resource constraints.

		higher-level resource specification models. - Tradeoff approach (requirements prioritization) expressed in a point-based prioritization system.	
UA	12	- User Credentials - Authentication token requests for validation (based on the KeyCloak documentation)	- Authentication tokens - Token validation status - User session status
AlaaS	13	- Domain knowledge (symbolic graph). - AIoT goals. - Training/runtime data (time series). - Models. - CaaS performance counters.	- AI model inferencing related to AIoT goals generated by the scenario.
CaaS	14	- Compute resource requirement or equivalent mapping.	- Compute resources for deployment of models.
IM	15	- Requirements from users.	- AIoT goals towards the AlaaS components.

4.5 Physical View – Initial Deployment Approach

This is an initial effort to make best use of the architecture definition in the design and actualization of the first integrated prototype of the PANDORA framework. This view encompasses the nodes that form the hardware topology on which the framework executes; it focuses on distribution, communication and provisioning. The software executes on a network of computers, or processing nodes. The various elements such as processes, tasks and objects need to be mapped to the nodes on which they execute. Computing IoT-Edge-Cloud resources and sensing infrastructure are described in this section.

We distinguish three layers in the Computing Continuum where software components may be operating. The IoT layer refers to sensors and IoT devices where some lightweight operations might be deployed. The Edge layer refers to computing resources that are deployed close to data sources (e.g., Edge servers, storage). Deploying components at the Edge fosters privacy by avoiding the dissemination of data outside of organizations. Finally, the Cloud layer offers powerful computing resources and provides a centralized control scheme for orchestrating PANDORA components.

Deployment diagrams

Identifying where software components operate across the computing continuum is crucial for understanding the system's behavior and performance characteristics. Components running closer to data sources offer increased privacy and lower response time, whereas components running on Cloud benefit from more powerful resources at the expense of a higher latency. We first identify core PANDORA components that are hosted on a centralized Cloud-based platform. These include UA, IM, AlaaS, CaaS, ADOA, CIM and DICE components.

Figure 28. Component Classification for Distributed AI Inferencing

Other components may be distributed across the computing continuum, depending on the intents and requirements provided by use case providers. This is coordinated through the CaaS, ADOA, and CIM components, which determine the optimal distribution to achieve the required intents. Figure 28 shows distributed AI inferencing operations, where the CRV component and models are distributed across the IoT, Edge, and Cloud layers. This distribution is determined through the ADOA component.

Figure 29. Component Classification for Non-Distributed AI Inferencing

Figure 29 shows a non-distributed inferencing scenario, where the FRML component and models are running on IoT devices, and the CRV component and models are hosted on Edge resources only.

5. Indicative Scenarios of Use

5.1 Use Case View – Use Cases Diagrams

SAG Scenarios

In addition to the four views discussed above, this is the central view for capturing scenarios. The Use Case View encompasses the use cases that describe the behavior of the framework as seen by its end users and other stakeholders. It also facilitates a clear understanding of the framework functionalities and it aids with the identification of user requirements, as well as ensures all stakeholders have a shared vision of the framework's capabilities and interactions. By illustrating the relationships and dependencies among different components and user interactions, Use Case diagrams play a crucial role in the successful design and development of PANDORA.

Figure 30. Use Case Diagram for SAG Scenarios

As shown in Figure 30, in SAG Scenario, users and anomaly detection applications interact through a set of processes. Users initially produce synthetic data within a simulated environment, creating data for predicting network conditions (SAG Scenario 1) or cycle time required to complete a full system scan (SAG Scenario 2). Raw data and generated synthetic data will be augmented by dimensionality reduction for training purposes. The inference models are then trained and deployed in a distributed environment. Based on the predictions, the models can issue reallocation commands to optimize performance—redirecting traffic through alternative network paths to mitigate potential delays in SAG Scenario 1 or reallocating relevant applications to servers with more resources in SAG Scenario 2. Finally, explanations as well as uncertainty assessments are shown to facilitate understanding of the AI models' decision-making processes.

SAG Scenario 1: High network traffic delay management

Figure 31. Sequence Diagram of “High network traffic delay management” in Phase 1

Figure 32. Sequence Diagram of “High network traffic delay management” in Phase 2

Figure 31 and Figure 32 present the sequence diagrams for SAG Scenario 1 in Phase 1 and Phase 2 respectively. In Phase 1, the tSDG component initiates the process by creating synthetic data of “normal” as well as “anomalous” data points that reflect infrastructure failures. Following this, feature analysis and dimensionality reduction techniques (DRFEC component) will be applied to retain only the most relevant information, ensuring efficient and accurate traffic delay

predictions by the AI model as well as enhancing its fidelity and relevance for use in Phase 2. The DEL component can provide insights into the synthetic data generation process, allowing operators to better understand its characteristics and limitations. In Phase 2, the augmented trustworthy dataset from Phase 1 is leveraged to support a proactive approach generation to managing network load. Here, the CRV component ensures that models can learn continuously from incoming runtime data to adapt to changes in network and production conditions. To train the continuously learning models from CRV, computational resources are requested from CaaS based on the training requirements to support the process. Once the models are trained, model registration and selection are performed in AlaaS in order to deploy the models. Then computational resources are requested again for CIM to generate inference efficiently. In addition, resources are also provided to FRLM component for model training in a federated environment and to ADOA to generate deployment plan across the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum. After the inferencing process, the DICE component provides explanations for continuous learning for end-users monitoring and controlling the production cell.

SAG Scenario 2: Cycle time efficiency optimization

Figure 33. Sequence Diagram of “Cycle time efficiency optimization” in Phase 1

Figure 34. Sequence Diagram of “Cycle time efficiency optimization” in Phase 2

Figure 33 and Figure 34 Alaa demonstrate the “Cycle time efficiency optimization” scenario. Similarly, the tSDG and DRFEC components are used in Phase 1 for synthetic data generation and data augmentation. While in Phase 2, the CRV and CIM components are used for continuous learning and inferencing. The FRLM component is leveraged to support federated learning and ADOA is

used to deploy AI models across the cloud-edge continuum. Finally, the inference is used to generate proper actions for the devices.

EAB Scenarios

Figure 35. Use Case Diagram for EAB Scenario

Figure 35 illustrates the use case diagram for EAB Scenario. In this scenario, end-users may define goals along with communication and movement constraints to create a safe navigation plan for the robot. As the plan is executed, the robot's behavior is continuously monitored to update its status within the environment and asks for new inferences for adapting the safe plan as needed.

EAB Scenario 1: Communication aware safe robot planning

Figure 36. Sequence Diagram of "Communication Aware Safe Robot Planning" in Phase 1

Figure 37. Sequence Diagram of “Communication Aware Safe Robot Planning” in Phase 2

As shown in Figure 36 and Figure 37, in Phase 1, tSDG component generates synthetic data related to the robot's status and its environment, including robot sensing data, SLAM data, and 5G performance datasets. This data is then augmented by the DACL component and validated through V&V processes to ensure accuracy and relevance. In Phase 2, the actor specifies intents, such as maintaining 5G throughput along the robot's path from location X to location Y. PANDORA processes this input, utilizing CRV for continuous learning and DICE for generating explanations, ultimately creating a safe plan for the robot to follow.

EAB Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control

Figure 38. Sequence Diagram of “Trustworthy closed loop communication control” in Phase 1

Figure 39. Sequence Diagram of “Trustworthy closed loop communication control” in Phase 2

Figure 38 and Figure 39 illustrate a scenario where 5G/6G communication can be managed to fulfill intents for various services. Similar to the previous scenario, the tSDG and DAL components are employed for synthetic data generation and data annotation. Additionally, DEL is utilized to explain the processes during phase 1. During Phase 2, the user must be authenticated before operating the system. Subsequently, distributed continuous learning is facilitated by CRV and ADOA, with DICE providing explanations for the inference at the end.

PCL Scenarios

Figure 40. Use Case Diagram for PCL Scenario

In PCL Scenario, the end-user defines the requirements and builds a demonstrator to collect images of inkjet-printed shavers. These collected images serve as the basis for generating synthetic images that encompass various types of anomalies. Continuous learning uses this data to generate an AI visual inspection model to detect anomalies of new printed shavers.

PCL Scenario 1: Automated Vision Inspection using product images

Figure 41. Sequence Diagram of “Automated Vision Inspection using product images” in Phase 1

Figure 42. Sequence Diagram of “Automated Vision Inspection using product images” in Phase 2

As shown in Figure 41 and Figure 42, in Phase 1 the collected images (including good products and defective products) are first classified by the QU-MAD component into different defect types. The vSDG component then generates synthetic images with DACL for data augmentation. In Phase 2, CRV is used for continuous learning and CIM is for accelerating the model training of CRV.

PCL Scenario 2: Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models

Figure 43. Sequence Diagram of “Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models” in Phase 1

Figure 44. Sequence Diagram of “Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models” in Phase 2

In the second scenario of PCL, compared to the first scenario, the focus shifts toward leveraging CAD drawings and 3D models for synthetic data generation during Phase 1. The generated synthetic data are used for continuous learning as presented above.

FRA Scenarios

Figure 45. Use Case Diagram for FRA Scenario

In the FRA Scenario, the end-user specifies the operational requirements and leverages a digital twin to simulate and test modifications in hydrogen refueling stations. This simulation helps predict parameters like temperature and pressure evolution under various conditions. The data generated from the simulations, combined with real-world operational data, is used to train AI models for predictive maintenance and operational safety. By integrating AI-based analytics, the system identifies hazardous states and predicts equipment failures, ensuring safe and efficient refueling operations while minimizing costs.

FRA Scenario 1: Increased operational safety assurance

Figure 46. Sequence Diagram of "Increased operational safety assurance" in Phase 1

Figure 47. Sequence Diagram of "Increased operational safety assurance" in Phase 2

Figure 46 and Figure 47 shows the scenario of optimizing the operational safety of hydrogen refueling stations. It uses the DACL, DRFEC components for data augmentation, the DACL component for explanations and the QU-MAD components for uncertainty quantification. In Phase 2, CRV is leveraged for continuous learning and DICE for explaining the inference.

FRA Scenario 2: Continuous system performance improvement

Figure 48. Sequence Diagram of “Continuous System Performance Improvement” in Phase 1

Figure 49. Sequence Diagram of “Continuous System Performance Improvement” in Phase 2

In this scenario, as shown in Figure 48 and Figure 49, is designed for continuous system performance improvement. Similarly, DEL, QU-MAD are used for data explanation and uncertainty analysis in Phase 1, as well as CRV is used for continuous learning in Phase 2.

HALCOR Scenarios

Figure 50. Use Case Diagram for HALCOR Scenario

Figure 50 shows the interaction between the users and extrusions in HALCOR’s Scenario. The users have to create a model that identifies consumption patterns in Phase 1 to collect energy consumption related data. The data collected from extrusions will be used to generate synthetic data like the previous components and then be used to predict energy consumption in the one hour future. The prediction, along with its confidence score and explanations will be shown to the users by a GUI at the end.

HALCOR Scenario 1: Next-hour(s) consumption prediction

Figure 51. Sequence Diagram of “Next-hour(s) Consumption Prediction” in Phase 1

Figure 52. Sequence Diagram of “Next-hour(s) Consumption Prediction” in Phase 2

As shown in Figure 51 and Figure 52, the collected data is enhanced using the DACL and DRFEC components. Afterwards, tSDG generates synthetic data using real-time observations and historical predictions as inputs and provides the generated dataset to DRFEC for critical features selection. In phase 2, end-users request for energy consumption prediction, and PANDORA leverages CRV for continuous learning, DICE for inference explanation, and CIM for accelerating the model training of CRV as previous scenarios.

HALCOR Scenario 2: Consumption estimation based on a production plan

Figure 53. Sequence Diagram of “Consumption Estimation Based on A Production Plan” in Phase 1

Figure 54. Sequence Diagram of “Consumption Estimation Based on A Production Plan” in Phase 2

Figure 53 and Figure 54 are about the second case of HALCOR to estimate energy consumption based on a production plan or a production schedule. In Phase 1, only DACL and DRFEC are used for data augmentation and explanations while in Phase 2, CIM and DICE are leveraged for explainable inference.

6. Integration Plan

6.1 Software Engineering Approach

Principles and Validation of the PANDORA solution

The proposed software engineering approach will apply a blend of agile/lean frameworks that focus on putting the user in the center of the solution construction process. In this way, by involving end-users from early stages, uncertainty will be reduced. In this sense, partners piloting the solution, will act as customers of the agile development process, thus participating during:

- The gathering of requirements.
- The prioritisation of requirements to be implemented, based on market value.
- The integration and validation of the concept and its correct operation.
- Feedback provisioning (back into design and implementation).
- The assessment of the solution from the technical and business perspective.

Following this approach, the design, the implementation and the validation happen in small iterations, i.e., they follow an iterative evolutionary approach. In this way, at the end of each iteration, there will be a working prototype, so that the effectiveness of the solution (methodology and services) will be evaluated by the use case users.

During the development of the project, PANDORA will provide business metrics to showcase the improvement achieved in relation to the software creation process for use case partners, and other social and business benefits for industrial partners, Information and communication technology (ICT) providers, end users, etc. Some other interesting metrics would be those related to PANDORA scientific and technical objectives, so that we can validate some of the expected aspects of the solution: efficiency, flexibility, extendibility, scalability, robustness, etc. An early prototype will be developed for testing and evaluating the key elements of the envisioned project results against the existing processes and infrastructures provided by the Use Case users and will aim at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 3. The testing of the early prototype will be made within experimental environments in the project use cases and will provide feedback about the functionalities that will be integrated into the Full Prototypes of the PANDORA solutions. Finally, to measure the global success of the project technical results, the Full Prototype will not only be testing the PANDORA solutions in an experimental environment, but it will also be configured for the assessment in real-life scenarios in each of the project use cases' environments. The measurement of all defined metrics and benefits will continue. During this phase, it is expected to achieve all defined targets and a TRL 5.

Methodology: Adaptive Project Management approach

For the development of PANDORA, the consortium proposes to follow an Adaptive Project Management (APM) approach. The reason for this is that PANDORA encloses a high complexity (due to the combination of leading-edge technologies), as well as high levels of uncertainty (due to the application of early software engineering theories that disrupt the current Software Engineering practice) and the APM approach has been designed to successfully manage complex projects with high levels of uncertainty.

In summary, APM combines the best practices of waterfall [3] and agile [4]. The former was designed to deal with complexity, but not uncertainty, while the latter was designed to deal with uncertainty and complexity. In this sense, APM manages risks and tracks the critical path while recognizing that our knowledge is incomplete at the beginning of the project, and it grows as the project advances. Making use of this methodology, the engineering tasks are organized as follows:

Waterfall approach

This approach will be followed during the first stage of the project, when the System Concept is designed. During this stage, the consortium will carry out the following tasks:

- Analyse the current state-of-the-art technology and market trends.
- Gather requirements from the project use cases.
- Design a generalized concept of the solutions based on the previous tasks.
- Describe the different sub-systems and services involved.
- Describe the features to implement.
- Identify and categorise the potential risks associated with hindering the successful implementation of the designed solution.

To the end, this concept will be used as a Minimum Viable Product that can be validated with the project use cases during the next stages of the project. The waterfall paradigm will be applied both in the first stage of the project as well as when the project comes to an end.

Agile approach

Following a SCRUM-like process, the next stages will be fully iterative for both the research activities and the implementation of the technological development. The work to be carried out under these WPs will be organized in monthly Sprints. The scope of each Sprint will be planned before its start, prioritizing the most critical issues (i.e. the issues that reduce the risks of highest impact, and provide the highest value to the end-users). Depending on the purpose, a Sprint can be devoted to:

- Experimentation. In this scenario, there can be several experimental/exploratory lanes running in parallel with the purpose of validating different hypotheses, exploring the technical capacities of a technology, or evaluating the viability of a specific feature. At the end of the sprint, the outcome would be an accepted or rejected hypothesis. If accepted, it could result in further development of a feature in next sprints, or in the adoption of a new technology.
- Implementation. When the purpose of the Sprint is non-experimental, the team will schedule the implementation of features at the planning session. The result of these Sprints will be functional prototypes of the sub-systems, services or features that will incrementally grow iteration after iteration. The RTD partners responsible for a technical feature will have an end-to-end responsibility, developing the full stack of the feature and testing it to demonstrate its correct operation. The partners acting as end-users of the solution will validate/accept the outcomes of each Sprint in their own contexts.
- Through these iterations we will incrementally gain knowledge about the final solution, and the process itself, providing lessons learned at the beginning of each sprint, and leaving room to schedule the implementation of new requirements (introduced by end-users, the market trends or other research projects).

In PANDORA we aim to adopt some elements of the waterfall and agile processes to develop the PANDORA framework; more details will be provided in D5.1 and D5.2. The prototypes resulting from the research and technological development stages will be integrated into a full prototype. This prototype will be validated in real business conditions in order to provide feedback to fix bugs (if necessary). To prevent critical issues at the integration stage, the end-users will be involved in the validation phase of each sprint.

It is important to remark that some tasks and WPs (such as the Architecture Definition, or the technical work packages), are expected to receive intense feedback during the last months of the project, i.e. after they are finalized. However, they will remain active until the end of the project, since they can obtain valuable feedback at any time during the project.

6.2 Continuous Integration & Deployment Process

To ensure fast, reliable and continuous delivery of the latest updates to teams involved in testing and development of the PANDORA tools, we designed and implemented a versatile and modern continuous integration and deployment process which is based on GitHub Actions.

Overview

The whole procedure consists of 3 stages as shown in Figure 55. Initially, a developer pushes changes to the main branch of a PANDORA GitHub repository. Our continuous integration infrastructure detects these changes and triggers a validation process, in order to confirm that everything works as expected without any issues. When validation finishes, all appropriate users receive an automated email that informs them about the validation result. The next action undertaken by the Continuous Integration infrastructure is to create new versions for each tool, by building them using the updated source code.

Figure 55. PANDORA CI/CD Workflow

Every PANDORA component follows a slightly different approach regarding the continuous integration and deployment process. However, for each component the result will be a deployable / installable tool. Exchange of data (e.g. models) will be realized through the PANDORA Integration Platform.

GitHub Integration

PANDORA components use GitHub repositories for the storage and versioning purposes of their project's source code and artefacts. Our Continuous Integration infrastructure must be able to initiate the integration and deployment processes for each project as soon as any new source code is pushed to the master branch of a project repository. This requirement is fulfilled thanks to the GitHub web-hooks. They allow external services to be notified when certain events, related to a GitHub project, happen. In this case, when a new commit is pushed to the master branch, our Continuous Integration infrastructure receives a call to a specific endpoint and triggers the appropriate process. As soon as this process finishes, the corresponding project readme files are updated so that they display the latest build status of the project.

6.3 Data/Model Input Requirements

This section presents an overview of the **Data/Model Input Requirements** per PANDORA component. For each component, we present the associated Use Case scenario derived from D2.3, and the corresponding requirements related to the specific data, ML models and in general input that each component needs to support the PANDORA use case scenarios.

Table 24. tSDG Input Requirements

tSDG Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C1-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The tSDG component requires as input: (1) an IoT dataset with network traffic data, (2) domain knowledge with the network topology and failure types (network traffic failures, vPLC control failures) in normal conditions, and (3) configuration parameters such as time intervals over normal conditions for the generated dataset.
C1-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	The tSDG component requires as input: (1) an IoT dataset with network traffic data, (2) domain knowledge with the network topology, the map of the smart space and failure types (network traffic failures, vPLC control failures) in normal conditions, and (3) configuration parameters such as time intervals over normal conditions for the generated dataset.
C1-03	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	The tSDG component requires as input: (1) an IoT dataset with robot sensing data and 5G network data, (2) domain knowledge with the map of the smart space, different types of smart spaces for simulation and different placement of obstacles in normal conditions, and (3) configuration parameters such as time intervals over normal conditions for the generated dataset.
C1-04	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	The tSDG component requires as input: (1) an IoT dataset with robot sensing data and 5G network data, (2) domain knowledge with the map of the smart space, different types of smart environments for simulation, areas with bad performance under certain user defined constraints (safety requirements, #users, antennas) and different placement of obstacles in normal/extreme conditions, and (3) configuration parameters such as time intervals over both normal and extreme conditions for the generated dataset.
C1-05	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	The tSDG component requires as input (1) a timestamped time-series dataset of historical energy consumption values. The dataset shall (2) consist of a minimum of one year of data to capture seasonality patterns (daily, weekly, monthly and/or yearly). The dataset may (3) incorporate domain knowledge, such as production plans, scheduled maintenance, or other relevant contextual factors.

Table 25. vSDG Input Requirements

vSDG Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C2-01	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	The vSDG requires as input: a) camera calibration data, b) sample images depicting defects and images without defects, c) the 3D model of the object to be inspected.
C2-02	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	

Table 26 QU-MAD Input Requirements

QU-MAD Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C3-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The component requires timestamped time-series data in CSV format, ideally with synchronized timestamps, including IoT dataset with network traffic data and configuration parameters such as time intervals defining normal conditions for the generated dataset. The dataset should include domain knowledge, about the network topology and failure types (e.g., network traffic failures, vPLC control failures) under normal operating conditions, both in the form of annotated/labeled data (e.g., high vs. low delay conditions) and descriptions of normal vs. anomalous network behavior. Additionally, data indicating critical situations or traffic spikes that may contribute to delays should be provided.
C3-02	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	The component requires a dataset that should consist of labeled images with each image being associated with a label specifying defect types and descriptions of normal vs. defective conditions. The images should ideally be diverse and balanced (as much as possible) and cover various defect types under different conditions. Relevant image metadata such as camera settings, lighting conditions, and production status can also be provided.
C3-03	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	The component requires a dataset that should consist of labeled images with each image being associated with a label specifying defect types and descriptions of normal vs. defective conditions. The images should ideally be diverse and balanced (as much as possible) and cover various defect types under different conditions.
C3-04	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	The component requires timestamped training data points provided in CSV format, ideally with synchronized timestamps. The dataset should include domain knowledge related to the scenario, incorporating both annotated/labeled information and descriptive material (e.g., definitions of normal vs. anomalous behavior). The data should have annotations/labels for anomaly types (both normal and abnormal conditions) and when there is no anomaly too.
C3-05	UC4S2	Continuous system performance improvement	
C3-06	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	The component requires timestamped time-series data in CSV format for training, ideally with synchronized timestamps, including historical energy consumption values. The dataset should incorporate domain knowledge, including both annotated/labeled information and descriptions of normal vs. anomalous behavior. Labeled data indicating anomalies or critical situations may be included for training the model to recognize deviations.

Table 27. DEL Input Requirements

DEL Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C4-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	DEL requires as input: (1) a timestamped IoT dataset with network traffic data, (2) domain knowledge with the network topology and failure types (network traffic failures, vPLC control failures) in normal conditions, and (3) configuration parameters such as time

			intervals over normal conditions for the generated dataset. Any available time series describing the behavior of the system. If available also a synthetic generator of time series will be a plus.
C4-02	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	DEL requires as input: (1) a timestamped IoT dataset with robot sensing data and 5G network data, (2) domain knowledge with the map of the smart space, different types of smart environments used as a reference, areas with bad performance under certain user-defined constraints (safety requirements, #users, antennas) and different placement of obstacles in normal/extreme conditions, and (3) configuration parameters such as time intervals over both normal and extreme conditions for the generated dataset. Time series availability describing the movements of robots would be needed. Domain knowledge about the goals that each robot has to achieve.
C4-03	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	DEL requires as input: (1) timestamped data about the UC that comes with (2) domain knowledge, both using (3) annotated/labeled information and as a set of descriptive material (what is good, what is bad, etc.). The dataset should contain (4) labeled data points corresponding to anomalies. Data should be in the format of time-series, when available, possibly with (5) indications of critical situations.
C4-04	UC4S2	Continuous system performance improvement	
C4-05	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	DEL requires as input: (1) timestamped data from the different synchronized sensors, (2) together with the energy consumption monitoring data at different time points, (3) domain and background knowledge about the ERP and production plans, (4) labeled data with error types when available, and (5) analytical tabular or csv data when available.

Table 28. DACL Input Requirements

DACL Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C5-01	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	The DACL component requires a dataset in the csv format (data table) that is partially annotated/labeled and whose data points contain partially missing feature values. The accuracy of the missing value inference (data imputation) and inferred annotations/missing labels (symbolic knowledge) directly depends on the number of complete data points with complete annotations.
C5-02	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	
C5-03	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	The DACL component requires a dataset of partially labeled images. Besides labeled images corresponding to normal data points (products without defects), the dataset should contain a certain fraction of images labeled with defect types for all defect types. The accuracy of automatic labeling w.r.t. a defect type directly depends on the number of images corresponding to that particular defect type.
C5-04	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	The DACL component requires a dataset of partially labeled images. Besides labeled images corresponding to normal data points (products without defects), the dataset should contain a certain fraction of images labeled with defect types for all defect types. The accuracy of automatic labeling w.r.t. a

			defect type directly depends on the number of images corresponding to that particular defect type.
C5-05	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	The DACL component requires a dataset in the csv format (data table) that is partially annotated/labeled. The dataset should contain labeled data points corresponding to anomalies.
C5-06	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	The DACL component requires a dataset in the csv format (data table) that contains data points with partially missing feature values. The accuracy of the missing value inference (data imputation) directly depends on the number of complete data points.
C5-07	UC5S2	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	

Table 29. DRFEC Input Requirements

DRFEC Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C6-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The DRFEC component requires the following inputs: an IoT dataset containing network traffic data, domain knowledge including network topology and known failure types (such as network traffic failures and vPLC control failures), and any additional time series data that describes the system's behavior. If available, synthetic time series data would also be beneficial.
C6-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	The DRFEC component requires the following inputs: an IoT dataset containing network traffic data, domain knowledge including network topology and known failure types (such as network traffic failures and vPLC control failures), and any additional time series data that describes the system's behavior and peak usage times. If available, synthetic time series data would also be beneficial.
C6-03	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	The DRFEC component requires time series data from the hydrogen refueling station, annotated with information on failures (anomalies, station shutdowns and other disruptions).
C6-04	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	The DRFEC component requires time series data reflecting the extrusion press's energy consumption past patterns.
C6-05	UC5S2	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	The DRFEC component requires time series data reflecting the extrusion press's energy consumption in relation to production planning

Table 30. CRV Input Requirements

CRV Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C7-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The CRV component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) to train and continuously update regression-based models predicting delay between vPLC and ET200. If data

			points are labeled (e.g., according to a threshold indicating high delays) then CRV will be able to train and update classification-based models for predicting high delays.
C7-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	The CRV component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) to train and continuously update regression-based models predicting cycle times of vPLC. If data points are labeled (e.g., according to a threshold indicating high cycle times) then CRV will be able to train and update classification-based models for predicting high cycle times.
C7-03	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	The CRV component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) for continual training of regression-based predictive models. Thresholds indicating significant deviations in throughput and latency should be provided.
C7-04	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	The CRV component requires labeled images in continuously delivered data batches for training and updating classification-based predictive models.
C7-05	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	The CRV component requires labeled images in continuously delivered data batches for training and updating classification-based predictive models.
C7-06	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	The CRV component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) to train and update anomaly detection models. If training data points are labeled then anomaly detection models will be trained and updated by supervised learning techniques, otherwise unsupervised learning techniques will be employed. It is expected that supervised anomaly detection models will perform better than unsupervised ones.
C7-07	UC4S2	Continuous system performance improvement	The CRV component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) to train and update classification-based predictive models that incrementally learn new anomaly types. All data points should be labeled, either as normal or by labels corresponding to anomaly types.
C7-08	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	The CRV component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) accompanied by variables reflecting the corresponding production plan to train and updated regression-based models predicting energy consumption.

Table 31. DICE Input Requirements

DICE Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C9-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The DICE component requires the time series that have been used as input to the CRV component, as well as the trained model the CRV has produced. It also needs the inference result (prediction, confidence score) for a specific data point (the one to be explained) by the continuous inference
C9-02	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	

C9-03	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	component (CIM), as well as an interval of previous data points and their corresponding predictions. When available, the DICE component requires as input the domain knowledge modeled as GENEOS libraries or causal structures from the DEL component.
C9-04	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	

Table 32. FRLM Input Requirements

FRLM Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C8-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The deployment infrastructure must contain more than one edge node device for federated learning clients and a server for federated learning coordination. Data points collected at each edge node should be in the same csv format (data tables with the same feature specification) and must be high-dimensional for representational learning.
C8-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	
C8-03	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	

Table 33. CIM Input Requirements

CIM Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C10-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	The CIM component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) to train and continuously update regression-based models predicting delay between vPLC and ET200. If data points are labeled (e.g., according to a threshold indicating high delays) then CRV will be able to train and update classification-based models for predicting high delays.
C10-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	The CIM component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) to train and continuously update regression-based models predicting cycle times of vPLC. If data points are labeled (e.g., according to a threshold indicating high cycle times) then CRV will be able to train and update classification-based models for predicting high cycle times.
C10-03	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	The CIM component requires labeled images in continuously delivered data batches for training and updating classification-based predictive models.
C10-04	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	
C10-05	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	The CIM component requires timestamped training data points in continuously delivered data batches in the csv format (data table) accompanied with variables reflecting the corresponding production plan to train regression-based models predicting energy consumption.
C10-06	UC5S2	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	

Table 34. ADOA Input Requirements

ADOA Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C11-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	ADOA needs the architecture for the model of the AI app as well as resource availability, specifications and topology (edge and cloud). In this case, ADOA ideally needs specific goals for network traffic delay metrics so as to compare its output to the reference values..
C11-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	
C11-03	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	
C11-04	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	ADOA needs the architecture for the model of the AI app as well as resource availability, specifications and topology (edge and cloud). In this case, ADOA ideally needs specific goals for trustworthiness metrics so as to compare its output to the reference values.

Table 35. UA Input Requirements

UA Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C15-01	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	User Credentials from User Interface, Token validation requests from components that need authentication.
C15-02	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	

Table 36. AlaaS Input Requirements

AlaaS Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C12-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	Inputs: (i) Goals from the intent manager component per use case (ii) Pre-trained models from phase 2 strategies (iii) Benchmark results on IoT-edge-cloud on phase 2 strategies (iv) Phase 1 datasets, if models are to be trained within AlaaS (v) Runtime data for model inferencing (vi) CaaS capacity and optimization to deploy inferencing.
C12-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	
C12-03	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	
C12-04	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	
C12-05	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	
C12-06	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	
C12-07	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	

C12-08	UC4S2	Continuous system performance improvement	
C12-09	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	
C12-10	UC5S2	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	

Table 37. CaaS Input Requirements

CaaS Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C13-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	Inputs: (i) Inference requirements from AlaaS (ii) Benchmarked model performance on various compute nodes (iii) Monitored real-time compute capacity for orchestration (iv) Capacity information shared with ADOA and/or CIM for inferencing efficiency.
C13-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	
C13-03	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	
C13-04	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	
C13-05	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	
C13-06	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	
C13-07	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	Inputs: (i) Inference requirements from AlaaS (ii) Benchmarked model performance on various compute nodes (iii) Monitored real-time compute capacity for orchestration.
C13-08	UC4S2	Continuous system performance improvement	
C13-09	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	Inputs: (i) Inference requirements from AlaaS (ii) Benchmarked model performance on various compute nodes (iii) Monitored real-time compute capacity for orchestration (iv) Capacity information shared with ADOA and/or CIM for inferencing efficiency.
C13-10	UC5S2	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	

Table 38. IM Input Requirements

IM Requirements			
Req. Id	UC and Scenario	Scenario Name	Data/Model Input Requirements
C14-01	UC1S1	High network traffic delay management	

C14-02	UC1S2	Cycle time efficiency optimization	<p>Inputs: (i) Requirements and thresholds (3GPP format compliant) to be ensured by the PANDORA system per use case (ii) Domain Knowledge to understand semantics of requirements (iii) Current state of the system to determine targets.</p>
C14-03	UC2S1	Communication aware safe robot planning	
C14-04	UC2S2	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	
C14-05	UC3S1	Automated Vision Inspection using product images	
C14-06	UC3S2	Automated Vision Inspection based on CAD drawings/3D models	
C14-07	UC4S1	Increased operational safety assurance	
C14-08	UC4S2	Continuous system performance improvement	
C14-09	UC5S1	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	
C14-10	UC5S2	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	

7. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the definition process followed to design the PANDORA framework architecture. Our focus is to present a solid architecture view, as well as to prepare the foundations for the subsequent tasks of development and integration that will follow. A comprehensive reference architecture is designed, providing detailed descriptions of its various components and their interactions.

The PANDORA architecture is designed to deliver advanced functionalities and services through a cohesive framework. The architecture describes the main components and their specifications, ensuring that each part aligns with the overall functionality goals. To confirm the proper interactions between the components of PANDORA, we gathered and documented all the necessary details of each component and designed the overall architecture using different views to bind business logic with technical requirements. The integration guidelines provide a preliminary blueprint for combining these technical elements into a unified framework. The document provides common strategies to accommodate future development. For each component, the necessary and available communication requirements have been discussed to align all technical partners for the data exchange mechanisms and interconnection methods inside the PANDORA framework.

Looking forward, this architectural framework represents the initial step towards integration, setting the stage for further modifications and refinements as the project progresses. The iterative nature of the integration process, aimed to be provided in D5.2, will ensure that the system adapts to new insights and intent requirements, maintaining the robust and continuous operation of AIoT applications. As a result, the framework presented in this document may be slightly adjusted during the integration phases and any modifications will be documented in subsequent deliverables.

In summary, this deliverable establishes a robust foundation for the PANDORA project's technical development, that will assist WP3, WP4 and WP5. The architecture defined here will guide future work packages, driving the project towards its ultimate goal of delivering innovative and reliable services to its end-users.

8. References

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